

Deliverable 4.2

Documentation of workshops and performances

2025

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Executive Summary

Deliverable 4.2- Documentation of workshops and performances

Developed within the Contested_Territory network, this deliverable systematises a range of **workshops and performances** framed within the tasks 4.4¹ and 4.5² of the Work Package N°4 of the project: “Connecting and reclaiming Contested Territories: The scope of co-producing alternatives”.

The collection of initiatives herein -all unique but also all intertwined in a network with a coherent manner of co-producing and bringing knowledge into practice- gives evidence of the synthesis that our core concepts, *otros saberes* and contestation, reach through our active and creative methodological options, our *otros haceres*.

Hence, in addition to the documentation of those experiences, this deliverable seeks to analyse, on the one hand, their methodologies, which comprise -in most cases- unorthodox and innovative research strategies, frequently in dialogue with the realm of the arts. And, on the other hand, their contribution with territorial contestation, which represents one of the backbone concepts of the project.

Even if each experience herein described is unique, some categories have emerged during the analysis of both workshops and performances: regarding **workshops**, the first debate we intend to enrich is whether they are community workshops and why. The second categorisation refers to the focus and techniques deployed to design and implement those workshops: although they are all inscribed within the scope of research strategies, some make use of conventional tools for co-producing and disseminating knowledge, while some others recur to performative and artistic tactics and techniques, some focus on the territory and the body, and others use the workshop mainly as a guiding thread, a platform for deploying and giving cohesion to a myriad of learning and researching resources.

As for **performances**, we discuss their particularities and distinctive elements, as much as its hybrid essence, and the connections and crossovers they present with other theatrical means of research.

Following the introduction in which we discuss the categories mentioned above, the deliverable presents all the initiatives in two sections, each with a short introductory reflection, followed by the catalogued experiences. The workshops section contains 13 entries, and the performances section 5, documenting more than 60 activities in total, all of them follow a standardized structure to ensure clarity and usability: it includes a concise summary of the initiative, a discussion on their contribution with contestation, and links to complementary materials, apart from illustrative images alongside most experiences.

[1] Task 4.4: **Developing small-scale community workshops**. Participatory community workshops in each partner country will explore the scope of co-producing innovative community practices that develop alternative understandings of humanity and nature. In workshops, a fusion of qualitative methods rooted in participatory action research will be used. This includes participatory mapping, but also different forms of knowledge such as oral history, music, poems and corporeal expressions to help developing the conflicting positions about the coexistence and interdependence of different forms of knowledge.

By this, we seek to unravel the ways through which spatial meanings are produced and negotiated in a context dominated by increasing demands for land rights. This task is central to understanding the political subjectivities behind reclaiming Contested Territories. We will also concentrate on how to appreciate and learn from the non-archival memory and affective connections of those affected by territorial accumulation, i.e. asking us how stories, experiences and knowledges can be validated in an ethical manner. Workshops may also include smart mapping to analyse and represent in a dynamic way the complexity and heterogeneity of Contested Territories, triggering spatial transformation and awareness.

[2] Task 4.5: **Reclaiming territories through art, performance and the visual**. This task explores community initiatives that aspire to co-create counter-hegemonic ways of producing social representation and social realities, focusing especially on the visual, artistic and performative character of this co-production. Research action will be decided with local communities, and it will apply popular knowledge about visual representation, art expressions and methods such as the ‘theatre of the oppressed’ to co-create knowledge that is meaningful to foster local initiatives, unravelling the boundaries between science, activism and arts.

Contested Territories is an international, cross-sector network of organizations from Europe and Latin America united in a joint research program focused on generating conceptual and empirical knowledge on territorial inequalities.

At Contested Territories, we believe that the alternative practices and knowledge promoted by communities are the basis for understanding the transformations of space and society, and enable the dissemination of knowledge in a movement that goes from the local to the global. We are particularly interested in investigating and understanding how communities themselves shape, negotiate, imagine, and collaboratively manage their territories within power relations that are always unequal and constantly contested.

The unifying concept of Contested Territories allows us to establish a consciously open and interpretive approach, based on seeking an understanding of the conflictual mechanisms and political disputes in the production and appropriation of different spaces and other knowledge anchored in the territory.

The teams that make up the network come from diverse geographies and disciplines, both academic and artistic, from research, territorial intervention, and cultural production. We seek to generate an exchange that allows us to understand, support, and offer alternatives to disputed territories.

Introduction

Workshops and performances: Otros haceres

The following document brings together various reflections derived from the systematisation of **workshops and performances**: a range of artistic, activist, cultural and community management practices deployed in the framework of the CONTESTED_TERRITORY project, an international and intersectoral network of 23 organisations from Europe and Latin America, gathered around a common research programme aimed at producing conceptual and empirical knowledge on territorial conflicts caused by unequal development, segregation, extractivism, dispossession and other injustice related phenomena.

The initiatives herein are part of Work Package 4, which proposes connecting the experiences of people claiming disputed territories and co-producing alternative knowledge through art, exploration of non-academical fields, and innovative paths for research. It also facilitates the active collaboration with local social organizations in the identification and implementation of self-organized social innovation projects as a means of contestation.³

In the process of documenting these experiences, we found a richness and diversity that is a true exponent of the spirit and values of the CT program:

- the will to build common languages to enable the dialogue between participants coming from multiple backgrounds, academic disciplines and non-formal knowledges -and sometimes, literally speaking different languages-,
- a quest going from the rigorous application of classic methods of scientific production, to the search for equally rigorous alternative and experimental methodologies⁴
- and the recognition of otros saberes a scope that goes from site-specific activities, to multi-locations and also remote virtual meetings.⁵

While all of the activities surveyed have been one of a kind, they have simultaneously constituted, as a whole, a consistent expression of this universe.

[3] In that sense, this deliverable is closely linked to two others: on the one hand, the Deliverable 5.1 Otros Saberes Toolkit, which focuses specifically on reflecting on the knowledge produced in research in territorial conflict settings and how these otros saberes have strengthened the commons, the capacity for resistance, and ultimately, community response to inequality. On the other hand, the Deliverable 5.2 Documentation of Community Workshops, which provides a specific analysis of these activities and their close connection with otros saberes and community contestation.

[4] For further information, visit Deliverable 2.2: Methods and training Toolkit <https://www.contested-territories.net/toolkit-approaching-contested-territories/>

[5] Many of them as a result of the impediments settled by COVID pandemics, and adopted since then as a valuable resource for such a geographically extensive network

All of them evidence how the recognition and construction of otros saberes require the use of innovative methodologies and implementation of alternative practices, or what we call **otros haceres**, and vice versa, these alternative practices are developed and informed by *otros saberes*.

“Otros saberes are understood here as innovative yet existing approaches to resource use and associated human-environment relations, values and knowledges that have been marginalised by mainstream academic and policy debates yet possess the potential for sustainability and transferability across different contexts. While otros saberes may be articulated in ordinary people’s everyday habitual practices, they often become most apparent through multi-stakeholder dialogues, exchanges, disputes and struggles in specific territories”. (Horn, P, Calsina Valenzuela, C.L., Zambrana, F., Dal Din, L. 2025).

Otros haceres are understood here not only as non-traditional research practices, such as PAR (participatory action research) and those which include, for example, feminist and decolonial approaches, but essentially those that bring the social realm into the centre of the scene, enacting and performing the diversity of community life, trespassing the limits between academy and territorial practice, in a constant dialogue between metodologías otras (alternative methodologies) and counter-hegemonic community actions.

The richness and diversity we encountered while documenting these experiences also highlighted the need for deeper methodological reflection: How is it that so many different activities are labeled as **workshops**? What, by definition, is their core essence? What are the varieties and limits of the concept? Likewise, the boundaries of the notion of **territorial performance** are many times diffuse, and overlap with those of other theatrical explorations, hence requiring some further explanation.

Workshops: community workshops, research workshops

Thus, the first step was to explore the scope of the concept of workshop and propose a distinction regarding **community workshops**⁴: the simplest option for delimiting them indicated that if they involved exclusively “members of the academic community”, they were technical workshops, and if they involved the “extramural community”, they were community-based. However, this reasoning would lead us into several contradictions with our theoretical and methodological framework

(sometimes Occam's razor, in its eagerness to clear away parsimony, can shave away the complexity, the multilayeredness, and the intertwined nature of social fabric).

As a first contradiction, this distinction seemed to reinforce the binary of formal/ academic knowledge versus other/ community knowledge, thus breaking with our purpose of articulating and co-producing knowledge, and emphasising -as it always occurs in binary thinking- the hierarchical nature of these two poles, leaving one (scientific knowledge) above the other (community knowledge).

Secondly, even if we had wished to mark it out, that line was not so easy to draw: what happens, for instance, when a researcher is also a member of the community? What happens when community experts teach/ share their knowledge with researchers? And what happens when new knowledge emerges -as it happens most frequently in CT network- from the articulation of formal and other forms of knowledge?

As a consequence, rather than on the participants, we decided to focus instead on the **contents** co-produced in the workshops and their **“direction”**. That is, we understand that a **workshop is community-based** when both the process and the product result in the construction of new knowledge for the community and/or fundamentally applicable within the community. On the contrary, if a knowledge (technical, academic, traditional or otro saber) is built or learned mainly within the academic community (researchers, students, teachers) and/or generates formal outputs applied mainly in academic settings or mixed settings, we understand **that the workshop is part of the research strategy and methodology**.

While this classification does not pretend to be strict, it contributes with meaningful debate about co-production and dissemination of knowledge generated through these methodological paths, and their contribution with contestation.

This deliverable focuses on the second group: **workshops as a research strategy**. In its section 1, you will find an introduction to the concept and a descriptive classification according to the techniques and aims involved.

[4] Community workshops are documented and analysed exhaustively in Deliverable 5.1

Workshops, performances and contestation

Apart from the particular contexts and projects in which they occur, each of these initiatives has the transversal aims of, on the one hand, enabling critical reflections on the traditional ways of producing knowledge and the role of research methodologies, and on the other hand, making concrete contributions with the multiple forms of resistance and contestation the communities present.

Based on participatory action research, all these activities framed within the Contested_Territory network, encourage collaboration between local communities and our project partners, seeking to strengthen the commons, the potential for proposing ethical, strategic and autonomous alternatives, through the creation of spaces of dialogue between different approaches to understand 'development'.

Strongly intertwined with stimulating visual and cultural forms of expressing embodied and lived knowledge, we aim at connecting the experiences of people reclaiming Contested Territories and co-producing alternative territories.

Over the past four years of practice and reflection on the convergence of multiple ways of being and knowing, the workshops, performances, and their outcomes have deepened our understanding of territorial conflicts and contestation. While documenting the experiences, we have collected the standpoints of the researchers regarding the theoretical concept of contestation, as well as the particular contribution the projects they led have made to it: the latter is expressed on each of the entries and the former has enriched the introductory reflection in both sections (for workshops and performances, respectively) and is also encapsulated in the word cloud that follows.

Section 1: Workshops

Workshops in research

From ancient times to the present day, in different parts of the world and multiple disciplines, the word "**workshop**" has been used to designate a myriad of things related to learning and work: the idea of a workshop may refer from a specific activity, to a series of them, from a meeting space to a methodology or a strategy.

The origins of the term were linked to the arts and crafts, rather than to science or academia, and generally involved one (or more) prestigious individuals, recognised as experts in their field, who brought together apprentices to train them by exercising those arts or crafts, this is, by actively participating in a common practice.

There is no precise evidence of how this concept came to designate as well informal and formal spaces for the production or exploration of knowledge, however it is currently used in a wide variety of (sometimes indiscriminate) ways, although, in any case, always presenting some distinctive elements: a collective space where the construction (of tangible or intangible products) and/or problem-solving are sought through the intersection of knowledge (theory) and actions (practice).

In the words of Agustín Cano, the **workshop** is:

"A group work device, with a fixed time-frame and carried out with certain particular objectives, enabling the activation of a pedagogical process based on the integration of theory and practice, participants protagonism, the dialogue of diverse knowledge, and the collective production of learning, bringing about a transformation both in the participants and in the initial situation." (Cano, A. 2012 pp.33, our translation)

Either as a single event, or as a part of a wider project, the **workshop as a research methodology** requires the researchers to work in a twofold role: as researcher (by producing and analysing data together with the other participants) and as a methodological facilitator.

Although the products (or outputs) are not only expected but required in any workshop, the analysis of the process of implementation is equally valued and registered: the guiding principle is "to learn while doing, and to do while learning". This sort of connection with the origins of the idea of workshop also shows in the use of time, or more precisely, its cadence, a particular -somehow, counter-cultural-

way of producing thinking: in the words of Lucas Soares (2025), un pensar artesanal, a craft-thinking, which implies not only an analytical, critical essence, but a slow one.

"Machine thinking (or as we would say today, algorithmic thinking, a product of computational thinking), automated, serial, and rushed, is expressed on a large scale in the hyper-technologized world (...). Craft-thinking functions as a sort of analytical anchor that allows us to investigate, among other things, how our daily lives have been reduced to an anxious, hyperactive, and self-demanding way of life governed by the logic of efficiency" (Soares, 2025. pp. 98, our translation)

This device, and the epistemological approach we describe herein, has been enriched with the theoretical and methodological contributions of several disciplines and methods, such as popular education, social psychology, and participatory action research -to name a few- and vice versa, it has been used from those and many other areas of knowledge as a tool for processes of social transformation.

Additionally, this collective way of co-production -based on an inherent intention of deconstruction of the naturalized representations- relies on reciprocity and diversity to enrich and empower the members, both individually and as a group, and aims to promote genuine and active participation of local communities and actors. This is based on the consideration that no-one arrives into the group with no knowledge at all -there is no such a thing as a tabula rasa- but everyone can make contributions into the research and co-creation of knowledge, departing either from previous formal learning, or from lived experiences and otros saberes, thus destabilizing the very ideas of science, knowledge and turning the academy itself into a contested territory.

Characterization

Beyond the shared elements in the workshop's conception and its epistemological framework, within the CT nodes we find an enormous richness of meanings and practices gathered under this name.

The workshop can be a technique or a strategy: that is, it can refer to the activity itself, or to a series of them, and/ or to the common thread that structures and enables other types of activities.

Additionally, the workshop may involve conventional techniques (more commonly utilised as well in formal environments), such as debates, conversatorios, critical readings, etc, or it may use alternative techniques like role-playing, artistic explorations, performative elements, and more.

Regarding the modality, the workshop had been traditionally territorially anchored, with a group sharing a physical space to carry it out. More recently, helped by the improvement of remote networking technologies, and also, by a quite forced creativity product of the COVID pandemics quarantines, workshops have been reshaped, allowing now a new mode as virtual or remote workshop (and/or hybrid) in addition to the face-to-face ones: a valuable resource for such a geographically extensive network as CONTESTED_TERRITORY.

In the course of documenting and analysing our workshops, some particularities have emerged that led us to characterise them (besides the distinction that we already mentioned in the introduction of this deliverable regarding community workshops). Although we are talking in all cases about workshops as a methodology for research, learning, and co-production of knowledge, we have grouped them according to those particularities as:

- **Technical workshops**
- **Creative exploration workshops**
- **Body-territory workshops**
- **Scaffold workshops**

We refer to **technical workshops** when they seek to explore, co-create, disseminate, share and acquire (formal or informal) knowledge. They reflect the most widely accepted understanding of what a workshop is, as defined by Cano (among others). They can utilize various, more or less conventional **techniques** structured within the workshop strategy, such as discussions, film screenings, thesis or poster presentations, critical readings, etc. Their focus is generally on thoughts and words as the “raw material”, and the use of the body is not essential for the co-production (actually, this is the kind of workshop that can be held remotely).

In this documentation of CT workshops, there are several examples of this variety. As single events, for example, the workshop on “Analysis of Speech on the research processes of territorial accumulation” (in FAUBA, Buenos Aires, Argentina), or the “International workshop to compare results of the *Encuesta Inquilina* (Tenants Survey)” (in IDRA, Barcelona, Spain). They have also proved useful as a moment of synthesis after different activities involving alternative techniques of research.

That is the case, for instance, of the analysis workshops -held in every case on the day immediately after the critical tours- in the Diálogos Sur-Sur encounters.

The purpose of **creative exploration workshops** is to acquire or practice a series of specific skills or techniques in audiovisual production, the arts (visual, musical, dance, theatre, etc.), or sensory perception, for use as a research methodology. They can either culminate in a concrete product (for example, an audiovisual or installation), or lay the groundwork for participants to later conduct research processes using the skills developed in their course.

As example, we would like to highlight experiences such as the workshop “Exploring the movement as a promoter of social change” held during the “*Metodologías otras*” gathering in Santiago de Chile, or “*Canto al agua*”, the workshop that took place in Pucón, during the “*Encuentros con el Agua*”. Along with others of this sort, these workshops brought into play explorations that are seldom taught in scientific circles and are even undervalued as forms of study and research, thus promoting an alternative form of exploration among the participating researchers. This constituted also a commitment to strengthening future opportunities, for example, of research through performances or theatrical representations.

Body-territory workshops: Their purpose is to explore the territory from a situated and critical perspective, using alternative techniques and grounded in situ.

They aim to explore the subjective dimension of the relationship with the territory but also does so through a group approach: it allows for a perspective based on the lived bodily experience in dialogue with peers and the environment.

They implement an embodied method and use techniques such as participatory mapping, other cartographies, and other forms of inquiry that allow for the development of new approaches.

Many of the initiatives herein documented have explored this variety of workshops, for example, with critical tours through contested territories (as the “walking reflections” held during the International Symposium: Coexistences and Struggles for the Inhabited Space”, in Colombia) or participatory mappings (like the one developed in ATERAL -territorial accumulation in Latin America- project, in Ecuador)

Finally, the **scaffold workshops** take their name after this image of the architectural techniques (which was originally used in constructivist pedagogy) since in a construction project, the scaffolding is not the technique, nor is it the main building material, nor is it even meant to be incorporated into the permanent structure of the building, but it is the support that makes possible the deployment of other techniques, skills and materials that make up the essence of the process and the product. In the case of what we call scaffold workshops, a multiplicity of techniques, strategies and activities are used for their development, but their planning and the common thread that allows the construction of the final product start from (or end in) a workshop.

Neither the most used strategies, nor the methodological essence of scaffold workshops are workshops strictly speaking (being instead, for example, interviews, podcast recording, audiovisual production, app development, etc.), but it is the workshop strategy that supports (sometimes intermittently) the methodological process. Like the architectural or engineering uses of the scaffold, it is common that the scaffold workshops gradually fade as the research process advances, giving space for the specific products to emerge. Such is the case, for instance, of the “Biochar filters project”, or the “Audiovisual summer school”.

This characterisation is flexible: is not meant to be closed, but, on the contrary, the edges of each category are porous, and sometimes overlap one with the next. We only proposed them because they were part of the methodological reflection that emerged when revisiting the experiences, and they were useful for grouping and exploring them in terms of technique/methodology.

Contributions to Contestation

Workshops are at the core of our research paths and methods, present in almost every initiative of our network seeking to co-produce knowledge, either as strategies, or as activities. With the traditions of PAR (participatory action research), popular education and social psychology (among others) as its tributaries, the workshop -in all its forms and varieties- nurture and structure our research projects, and contribute in many ways to contestation.

All through the analysis of these experiences, we observe that workshops, as one of the preferred and more used techniques of research in our network,

facilitate the co-production of new senses and meanings in the participant groups and collectives (including the academic community). Paraphrasing Oscar Jara (2010), we see that:

- Firstly, they are able to imagine other worlds and territories, breaking with the imposition of the existing order as the only historical possibility.
- Secondly, they are also able to question stereotypes and patterns which are presented as absolute truths (e.g. individualism, competition, the market as the regulator of human relations).
- Thirdly, people are able to continuously learn and unlearn.
- Fourthly, people are able to imagine and create new spaces and relations between human beings (...) and environmental surroundings.
- Finally, [they are able to overcome] a patriarchal and misogynistic socialization of gender and build new power relations in their everyday lives and in the system of social, political and cultural relations.

Additionally, as stated above, the horizontal dynamics of the workshops propitiate a participative, democratic co-production of knowledge and design of strategies for resistance, thus empowering the collectives in their territorial contestations. They also put into tension the sheer essence of scientific production, and somehow contribute to this other aspect of the contestation: the one in the main territory of the academy.

The experiences

Some of the experiences were documented elsewhere and there were some projects still ongoing by the end of this edition, including some workshops (and performances), and consequently, not all the workshops are systematised here.

However, this Deliverable documents and analyses more than 50 workshops, framed within 13 different initiatives from the CT network: a very representative sample of the diversity and richness of our work.

Each entry has a similar organisation to facilitate the reading and comparative analysis, stating the general information, the context and description of the experience, its contribution to contestation and links to help those interested in further exploring the projects.

Members of the CONTESTED_TERRITORY network at the gathering

ATERAL - Territorial accumulation in Latin America

Lead network node

France Node (CNRS – Toulouse and IRD – París)
Facultad Latinoamericana de Ciencias Sociales -
FLACSO (Ecuador)

Participating actors

Representatives of the nodes: University of
Sheffield (UK) Pontificia Universidad
Javeriana Cali (Colombia)

Context of the activity

The activity brought together experiences on forms of territorial accumulation taking place on different margins (urban, regional, social). Referring to the example and common experience of the southern Ecuadorian Amazon, the activities taking place in mid-November 2024 with different actors in this region were aimed at sharing experiences, tensions, contradictions and topics anchored in the trajectories of the researchers involved.

The encounter included a workshop, a community workshop and two other activities of investigation on otros saberes, not recognised by the dominant actors. In the case of Amazonia South, knowledge about risks, technical, expert, modern, rationalised, evidence-based and measured knowledge, etc.

The activity arose in response to a persistent and structural conflict rooted in the disregard and erasure of local knowledge by dominant public actors, particularly concerning territorial risk and vulnerability.

In the southern Ecuadorian Amazon, communities face growing threats—such as the risk of rising water levels and flooding—that demand urgent attention and coordinated public intervention. However, official institutions have largely failed to recognise or act upon the knowledge and alerts coming from those directly affected.

Timeframe

The activity took place in mid-November 2024 in Southern Ecuadorian Amazon, Ecuador.

Other representatives: State University of Amazonia, organised neighbourhood communities and municipal and local authorities

Territory

Ecuador
Amazonian provinces

The conflict that underpins this activity stems from this neglect: the disconnect between public authorities and the lived realities of communities confronting environmental risks. Local forms of knowledge, often developed through generations of cohabitation with the territory, are excluded from institutional decision-making processes.

This exclusion not only marginalises communities but also worsens their exposure to danger by preventing effective, timely responses to environmental crises.

Description of the activity

This **body-territory workshop** was structured around three interconnected components –participatory mapping, observations, and field visits– designed to engage with and recover local forms of knowledge regarding territorial risk and territorial accumulation in the southern Ecuadorian Amazon.

A systematic observation was carried out during the workshops and related activities. Researchers observed interactions, spatial dynamics, and communicative practices to better understand how knowledge is shared, contested, and embodied in the community. Particular attention was paid to how risk is perceived and discussed by participants, and how it relates to everyday practices of territorial care and adaptation. Observation also helped document the tensions between local narratives and institutional discourses, revealing layers of conflict and resilience.

Field visits were conducted to key sites identified by community members during the participatory mapping and discussions. These visits allowed for a direct engagement with the physical landscape, grounding the discussions in the material conditions. The fieldwork served both as a method of verification and as an opportunity for joint reflection among researchers and local actors, strengthening the collaborative dimension of the activity.

Purpose

The activity aimed to collectively explore and make visible forms of territorial accumulation and environmental risk experienced by communities on

the margins—urban, regional, and social—in the southern Ecuadorian Amazon. Specifically, it aimed to recover and legitimise local knowledge systems that are often disregarded by dominant public actors, (particularly in relation to territorial vulnerability and the impacts of rising water levels), challenging the disconnect between institutional responses and the realities of affected populations. Ultimately, the initiative aimed to strengthen collaborative knowledge production and contribute to more inclusive and responsive forms of territorial governance.

The objective of ATERAL was to bring together CONTESTED_TERRITORY members to:

- Exchange on multiple forms of alternative territorial accumulation from both spatial (Amazonia, Patagonia, Esmeraldas, borders, etc.) and social (indigenous, women, migrants, etc.) perspectives;
- Consolidate a matrix of interpretation of territorial accumulation emphasising the immaterial and material features of the territories (symbolic, epistemological, cultural resources, etc.);
- Organise and systematise alternative development proposals from marginalised or contested territorial accumulation experiences in Latin America, based on the collection of case studies.

Screen shot <https://www.contested-territories.net/atlas/por-pais/ecuador/>

Contributions to the contestation

The activity identified a conceptual and epistemological space of contestation, and also a physical space, where opposing views and arguments materialise (in land invasion, for example). The seminar activated a dialectical process and tried to gather the knowledge accumulated by the community's experience: for example, we have seen how the community, devoid of any instrument of measurement or anticipation, can identify when the rising water level is dangerous for the neighbourhood, and when it is necessary to evacuate. This knowledge was then critically systematised and returned to the community (communities > technicians > communities), to continue monitoring the risk issue in dialogue with the municipality.

We also saw how within the community there are heterogeneous voices that are outbreaks of protest, and that prevent a single voice from speaking "for" the community, and thus identifying a potential for contestation.

Further information

[Encuentro Internacional Contested Territories
Amazonía - Región Sur 2024](#)

La GranColombia's leader, Erika Chica, during the workshop

GranColombia's leaders, FLACSO and CT members during the gathering

Analysis of speech on the research processes of territorial accumulation

Lead network node

Faculty of Agronomy - University of Buenos Aires, Argentina

Timeframe

November 2024, Buenos Aires, Argentina

Participating actors

Representatives of the nodes: CEUR (Centro de Estudios Urbanos y Regionales), Argentina. UAM (Universidad Autónoma de Madrid), Spain. Researchers (trainee, junior and senior) from Buenos Aires Contested Territories nodes.

General information

This **technical workshop** aimed to contribute toward a deeper knowledge on how to analyse discourses produced in the processes of territorial accumulation, with a focus on popular struggles against different kinds of extractivisms, neoliberal conservation policies, short agro-ecological production chains and their distribution in “alternative” channels.

The workshop took place at the Cátedra de Extensión y Sociología Rural of Facultad de Agronomía (University of Buenos Aires), in collaboration with CEUR (Centro de Estudios Urbanos y Regionales) and UAM (Universidad Autónoma de Madrid).

Context of the activity

The context of conflict at the heart of this initiative revolves around the discourses, policies, and material chains that structure agricultural production and distribution today, along with broader patterns of extractivism—practices that prioritize the exploitation of land, labor, and natural resources for profit, often at the expense of ecological balance and social justice. Through collective dialogue, the spare event of the workshop aimed to interrogate how policies and discourses affect material realities on the ground, and how grassroots movements are not only resisting but also proposing transformative alternatives to extractivist agriculture.

Description of the activity

The activity was based on a Foucault-inspired approach to discourse analysis, understanding discourses as fields of power and sites of social conflict. It provided some tools to critically read how discourse shapes and is shaped by power relations, and how it operates in the construction of social and environmental realities. Through this lens, participants examined dominant narratives—particularly those rooted in neoliberal and colonial logics—and engaged with alternative knowledges that challenge these hegemonic frameworks.

Territory

Argentina
Buenos Aires metropolitan area

The activity combined theoretical input with practical exercises to equip participants with tools to identify, analyze, and produce counter-hegemonic discourses in their own research and territorial engagement.

Purpose

The purpose of the activity was to provide both theoretical and practical training in discourse analysis, with a focus on developing tools to critically examine the discourses that emerge from processes of territorial accumulation, particularly in their environmental dimension. This approach enables participants to understand and analyze how language shapes and reflects power relations, environmental conflicts, and socio-territorial struggles.

Outputs and contributions to the contestation

The activity contributed to the contestation by analyzing both public and institutional discourses identified by the participants as central to their research, as well as counter-hegemonic discourses emerging from social struggles.

The workshop focused on alternatives and resistance to neoliberal and colonial narratives, particularly in the context of environmental and territorial conflicts. In all of them, it was unveiled how the processes of accumulation of territorial, social, cultural, and linguistic commons build alternative communicative relationships and practices to neoliberal governmentality.

it was unveiled how the processes of accumulation of territorial, social, cultural, and linguistic commons build alternative communicative relationships and practices to neoliberal governmentality.

As a key output, it provided participants with theoretical and practical tools for the analysis of social reality and for the design of discourses of contestation, thereby strengthening their capacity to critically engage with dominant narratives and support transformative processes.

Further information

El análisis de discurso como herramienta para estudiar procesos y conflictos urbanos.
Entrevista a Luisa Martín Rojo

Diálogos Sur-Sur: Other ways of inhabiting and representing the Territory

CT members visiting the Cholets

Lead network node

IIADI, Bolivia

Participating actors

Representatives of the nodes: Universidad de Chile, Chile. FLACSO, Ecuador. Universidad de Buenos Aires, Argentina. Universidad Javeriana de Cali, Colombia. Universidad de la Frontera, Chile. Politécnico de Milán, Italy. University of Sheffield, United Kingdom. Universidad de Madrid, Spain. CEUR/CONICET, Argentina. Karlsruhe Institute für Technologie, Germany. CEPLAG, Bolivia. Ciudades Reveladas. Basurama, Spain.

Context of the activity

Diálogos SUR-SUR was an initiative conceived to provide a space to establish a South-to-South dialogue, to exchange experiences and sociocultural practices around other ways of doing -otros haceres-, living, being, inhabiting and representing the territory that the indigenous dimension evokes in the current Latin American reality.

In this framework and after a series of preliminary remote meetings, the event convened different researchers-activists from various CONTESTED_TERRITORY nodes of South Latin America to talk, experience, and explore the territory.

The dialogue that started from there, allowed to critically look at some of the tensions and disputes of the South context, identifying similarities and differences between the different territories represented in the meetings.

Timeframe

The initiative took place in two different sessions in the city of La Paz, El Alto and Achocalla (Bolivia) in Autumn 2023 and Autumn 2024

Other representatives: Institutional actors (Municipal Government of La Paz and Municipal Government of El Alto); Trono youth art collective; Indigenous/indigenist youth collectives: Red K-motes del Tarwi, Red de la Diversidad, Colectivo Curva, Colectivo JICHA, Ayllus urbanos Nina Mayu. Community members of Alto Milluni, upper part of the Katari Basin;

Territory

Bolivia
la Paz, El Alto

The axes of analysis have been: 1. Worldviews and territorial tensions in urban/rural contexts 2. Symbolic and territorial disputes within indigenous ritual spaces 3. Artistic interventions (of the indigenous in urban contexts, a look at the experience in Latin America) 4. Ways of inhabiting the everyday from the Andean and indigenous perspectives - Habitat production.

Purpose

The Dialogos Sur Sur aimed to prove that despite the modernisation, and somewhat superficiality of the current society, different visions and perspectives survive in other ways of living, imagining, relating and representing the territory, the world and life of the peoples of the Andes. The activities addressed Latin American societal challenges and contrasts through critical journeys, highlighting the need to rethink the categories we use to name and understand territories, especially those shaped by colonial and civilising logics.

Many of these territories remain in fact deeply influenced by other ways of inhabiting and representing space, a contrast that becomes particularly evident in urban contexts, where different ways of naming, living, and understanding the territory not only persist but continue to shape everyday life. In this sense, the activities staged and made visible an enduring otherness—an otherness rooted in and expressed through the territory.

The initiative was extremely fruitful, setting off a series of derived outputs, and had an iteration of the gathering one year after the first one.

First edition

General info: La Paz, El Alto and Achocalla, Bolivia. From 24 to 28 April, 2023

Organisation of the event:

It was structured through 4 components:

1. Workshops exploring and experiencing the territory
2. Workshops on ongoing doctoral theses
3. The creation of a networking space to advance work in progress and imagine new collaborations between nodes for future research: Diálogos Sur-Sur and Mapoteca
4. Audiovisual and graphic productions.

Description of the workshops:

Body-territory workshops: During the first three days of the encounter, the workshops started with critical journeys: these have been spaces for navigating the territory, walking through its zones, streets, and places, while recognizing the daily, tense, and contested narratives.

It was basically about walking, but staging critical readings of the territory that allowed us to recognize the history, the colonial, symbolic, and material tensions that run through the territory.

They integrated moments of interaction and dialogue with actors: spaces for exploring the field of action of the experiences and their actors, and thus being able to reinterpret them, recognizing the meanings present in their struggle and territorial experience.

The theme of the workshops was the alternative representations and ways of inhabiting the territory.

On the first day, the focus was the ritual and ceremonial dimensions. The visits included:

- The **General Cemetery**, located in a popular neighbourhood of La Paz. There the participants learned about the festival of the Ñatitas which, unlike the religious festival “Day of the Dead,” integrates Andean rituals and narratives, thereby displaying a distinct relationship between life and death.
- The **Apachetas and Yatiris** of El Alto, where the locals researchers helped the visiting researchers to find out, mingled in the urban buildings, these altars for offers to the achachilas (the ancient spirits of the ancestors), and discussed the meanings of both sites and offerings.

Making an offering at Alto Milluni.

- **Paka Illa cultural centre**, located in the community of Uypaka within the municipality of Achocalla, including the participation in a special ritual held in the "**chullpares**" (ancestral burial sites conceived nowadays as sacred places) and in an **astronomical night** to appreciate Andean star constellations, and debate on their meanings and uses.

The second day, the aim was to explore Habitat, Andean architecture and the revitalization of culture. The workshops went by the **cable-car** (a point of interest on its own) around:

- The **Contemporary Art Museum** of El Alto: to put into context the aesthetical and artistic framework of contemporary aymara and criolla populations of this city.
- The **cholets**, a neologism that comes from mixing the word "chalet" and "cholo", and describes this singular contemporary Neo-Andean architecture.
- **Wayna Tambo** cultural collective, zona Villa Dolores. A space for the youth and a think tank for the new social, architectural and aesthetic movements that grew in the city in the last few decades.

Alto Milluni villages, with their community tourism initiatives.

The third day, the theme was Water, springs and other urban-rural links. The visits took place in:

- **Hampaturi village and dam**. The participants were taken through the productive dynamics of the "rurban" families. In the dam, there was a replica of the SILENCIO performance (see next section).

- **Urban springs of Pasankeri**: where the washer-women explained their struggles, and how they organised their collective reclaiming for an adequate infrastructure for their traditional work.
- **Urban Yapus and Ayllus of Alto Tacagua**: Here the participants learned that yapus and ayllus are productive gardens, the difference being that while the former include a sense of ritual and ancient knowledge, the latter do not, and are more like an hybrid form of urban yapus.
- The organisation **Nina Mayu Urban Ayllu**, also in Tacagua, where they promote potato cultivation based on collective agricultural principles grounded in the Andean community organisation of the ayllu.

After three days of these **body-territory workshops**, the closure came through technical workshops held on days 4 and 5, where -having as a guiding title "the accumulations, tensions, and territorial disputes"- the participants shared the lessons learnt, the highlights, the feelings and the open debates, comparing these experiences with those in their places of research.

Outputs and further info

The gathering enabled the production of 7 short films entitled PACHA: TERRITORIES WITH MEMORY. A survey of other perspectives on the territory from the communities of thought present in the territory. Available here: [Pacha: territorios con memoria](#)

There also was a short photographic document "Living Memory" by Mónica Cataño of the Cali node, linking the work she does in Colombia and the experience of the *Diálogos Sur-Sur*, a photo gallery showcasing these other ways of inhabiting the territory and the symbolic and material disputes and tensions surrounding it, and a photo story about the Cable Car, focusing on rational and sensitive positions, and the experience of exploring the city via the Cable Car.

Video-memory of the Meeting: [DIALOGOS SUR-CORREG-FULLHD-final.mp4](#)

Second Edition

General info: La Paz and El Alto, Bolivia. From March 25 to April 12, 2024.

Organisation of the event:

It was structured through 5 components:

1. Workshops exploring and experiencing the territory
2. Workshops on ongoing doctoral theses
3. Three specialist talks open to the public, to disseminate the network's research advances through public discussions;
4. A networking space to evaluate work in progress and imagine new collaborations between nodes for future research: Diálogos Sur-Sur and Mapoteca
5. An audiovisual exhibition named "Audiovisual Territories"

Description of the workshops

The workshop activity was nourished by: pre-meetings (to share ideas, reflections, perspectives and views from the different territories); participatory dialogues, to invite the participation of different voices, different experiences and perspectives on the experience of being indigenous in the city; talks with expert voices or specialists in subject of territorial accumulation and resistance and part of the CT Network.

Body-territory workshops

Description of the activity: Being this encounter longer than the first one, the organisation of the workshops required some adjusting: Instead of having all the **body-territory** ones firstly, and lastly the technical space, it was arranged to have an intertwined dynamics alternating one of each.

Critical tours: the tours were **body-territory workshops** aimed at transiting the territory, walking through its areas, streets, places, while recognising the daily, tense and disputed narratives. This activity stages critical readings that help to recognise the history, the colonial, symbolic and material tensions that cross the territory. Collective, semi-structured walks of territorial recognition were carried out with selected points of rest and dialogue with predefined objectives. Walking to observe, record and understand the inequalities and other tensions present in physical spaces and social interactions, but also to dialogue with otros saberes of local actors.

This method was used to recognise women's experience of travelling by public transport, to observe the urban-rural continuum, the rural components and marks present in the city, to discover the watercourses transformed and hidden by urbanisation, and to get to know emblematic places of resistance struggles in the city of El Alto.

The points of visit were structured, accordingly, on 5 different modules:

- **Module 1: Gender and mobility.** Departing from Amarillo Sopocachi by cable car, the participants explored mobility with a gender perspective, recognized how women have a different experience of the city and identified some of the strategies they must implement to overcome the obstacles presented by cities designed for men.
- **Module 2: Multilocality.** In this workshop, the members were divided into four teams of six people each. Each team visited two territories of La Paz or El Alto, and they were asked to capture their experience via various audiovisual and graphic techniques
- **Module 3: Infrastructure of extractivism:** Visit to Milluni, cuenca Katari, where *otros saberes* regarding community life in spaces impacted by extractivism were also identified.
- **Module 4: Environment, contamination, water:** Where "Andar como si fueras agua" (Walk as if you were water) tour demonstrated other local knowledge about waterways (springs, memories of the presence of streams and irrigation ditches before urbanization, practices related to the presence of water)
- **Module 5: Young indigenous in the city.** In the critical walk through El Alto, the participants learned about the experience of living in the city from the perspective of indigenous youth.

CT members attend to a technical workshop

The **analysis workshops** -held in every case on the day immediately after the critical tours- have been spaces for dialogue and reflection where participants and representatives of the different nodes put their impressions, perspectives and readings about the territory on the table, based on the experiences carried out in Bolivia. This allowed a work based on practice, action and reflection, stemming from the experience generated in the territory.

Technical workshops: The Seminars

Technical workshops were used to promote exchange between doctoral students and experienced researchers (teachers), on the basis that these well-guided spaces can promote learning and dialogue, and because this method is student-centred. The workshop was conceived as a space in which to listen and give feedback on the progress and doubts of research processes.

They were organised in three groups, one per day:

- Group 1: Development and poverty
- Group 2: Infrastructure and urbanization
- Group 3: State, power and struggle:

Exploring the "Chullpares" (ancient burial sites) in Achocalla.

Technical workshops: Methodological workshops for doctoral students

In the same spirit, there were three spaces for teaching and learning.

- Dialogic Territories - Audiovisual Methodologies in Social Research and Militant Practices, facilitated by Khalil Esteban, UBA.
- Deep cartographies, facilitated by Malú Cayetano, Basurama.
- Bibliometric tools for the state of the art, facilitated by Ignacio Arce, Universidad de Chile.

Further information:

[Memoria Viva by monica marion cataño - Issuu](#)

[D2M2 - Programa FINAL 23-03-24 - Patricia Urquieta.pdf](#)

[Visit to Milluni \(module 4\): https://www.facebook.com/IIADIOficial/videos/7784569464955846](#)

Contributions to the contestation

The possibility of opening this research space opened the door to recognising the depth and mix that the territory lives every day and how the symbolic dimension, the tensions and territorial disputes are present in these spaces. It was possible to recognise the specific forms or territorial responses that exist today as a response to hegemonic narratives: experiences, looks and reflections that can build -or are already building- their path in aesthetic, narrative and reflective terms.

The territorial experiences that arise from the Andean indigenous heritage are an alternative response to a civic model that has been imposed over time and shows its anachronism, its limits and its collateral costs today. This idea emerges from the need to make visible and compare the tensions, disputes, and territorial, symbolic, and material accumulations that arise from the coexistence of indigenous otherness and modern rationality.

Above all, it is impossible to think about territory without also thinking about history, subjects, memory, and the ongoing struggles and conflicts that inhabit it. Territories are not empty or static spaces; they are living and dynamic fields, in movement.

Through critical experiential journeys and restitution, the research topics explored with these activities were: women's challenges in daily mobility; multi-localities as an expression of urban-rural links, strategies for maintaining territories, cultural patterns and food security; extractivism, pollution and the resistance of communities that develop community-led tourism projects as a response and alternative to extraction; water and urbanisation, the recovery of neighbourhood spaces for planting food and the reconstruction of collective knowledge and practices from the Aymara cosmovision present in the territory; the life strategies of young indigenous people in the city.

The various activities addressed and identified many forms of contestation, bringing together different representatives and community experiences, such as the Wayna Tambo - Network of diversity, the PAKA ILLA Center, and the collective NINA MAYU. The participants in the activities were able to meet the actors directly involved in these challenges, recognise their struggle and the purposes of their contestation.

Overall, the initiative produced learning outcomes based on dialogue between different knowledge and as a product of the multidimensional experience of territorial analysis.

The *Diálogos Sur-Sur* started an honest and horizontal dialogue to build a response to contemporary challenges from a plural vision of the territory, in an interdisciplinary reading, where these other knowledges are recognised for their epistemological and ontological value.

The group of participants after the body-territory workshop at the Cemetery

Encounters with Water: Epistemological, artistic and political contestations from the Mallolafken

Lead network node

Universidad de la Frontera, Chile

Participating actors

Representatives of the nodes: FLACSO (Ecuador), University of Leeds and University of Sheffield (United Kingdom) and Left Hand Rotation (Portugal).

Participatory critical cartography at the workshop: "Memoria: Voz de un territorio"

Context of the activities

Encuentros con el Agua was an event that aimed to explore different perspectives to destabilize the traditional ways for comprehension of and bonding with nature, the elements, and most particularly, water.

During the *Encuentros*, there was a myriad of debates and analysis organised in three interwoven dimensions: epistemological perspectives, methodological experiences, and political experiences. These three axes were addressed through roundtable discussions, workshops, and other practical experiences that put into tension different notions of WATER as a resource, as a commodity, as a vital element, as site: as a contested territory.

Timeframe

Pucón, Chile, November 2022

Other representatives: approx. 100 participants from territories near Pucón (Chile), including activists, students, Indigenous communities and citizens. Two Indigenous youth activists from El Alto (Bolivia) and Santa Clara canton (Ecuador).

Territory

Chile
Pucón

Along with other problems shared widely with other regions, the Mallolafken has a particular conflict with tourism and gentrification related pollution which was brought into attention during the gathering.

During three days, the intense programme of activities ranged from cultural and artistic shows to debates. It included some community workshops,⁷ as well as a series of performative actions and workshops that nurtured the final act for the gathering: the performance SILENCIO.⁸ Herein we present four workshops that explored in different ways the topics of the gathering.

[7] Community workshops are documented and analysed exhaustively in Deliverable 5.1

[8] Addressed in the next section along with the performance SILENCIO

Description

There were four workshops that facilitated the exploration of the epistemological perspectives, methodological experiences, and political experiences of water, through unconventional approaches: “*Memoria: Voz de un territorio*” by Marcela Urzay Rates and América Irribarra, “*Contemporary dance CUERPO LÍQUIDO*” (Liquid body) by Plataforma Azul, and “*Observation and painting*” by Soledad Gattavara and “*ITROFILL KÜME KO*” (or “*The kindness of water in all its shapes*”) coordinated by Wüfko corporation.

Workshop: “*Memoria: Voz de un territorio*”

The starting point of this **technical workshop** was an Exhibition presenting the project “*Memories of Water by Ancient Inhabitants of Pucón*”, and some of its outputs and products, such as the audiovisual capsule, the participatory critical cartography, and one of the radio play’s chapters, facilitating and ulterior mediation and analysis of the methodology used for the research and a debate on the work and the resulting objects, thus inviting a crossover between their content and possible paths to reach them, opening the exchange of creative and investigative experiences with the meeting participants.

Workshop: “*Itrofill küme ko*” (or “*The kindness of water in all its shapes*”)

It consisted of a **creative exploration** workshop, with performative elements and several different artistic forms, that explored the richness of the language of water in the Mapuche world through artistic expression.

Workshop: “*Contemporary dance CUERPO LÍQUIDO*” (Liquid body)

Flyers and social media used for invitation and dissemination of the Encounter

Workshop: “*Contemporary dance CUERPO LÍQUIDO*” (Liquid body)

This **creative exploration** workshop served as a training for contemporary dance that through Kinesiology, Flying Low, Floorwork and Release body techniques aimed to give greater awareness in movement to expand the horizons of personal and group corporality, enrich body language, and understand the body and movement in a more versatile way. It focused on the search for the relationship of the body with the ground, integrating it as an internal support and basic technical tool.

The choreographic phrasings attend to the practice of organic movement patterns from which we find spirals of energy inside and outside the body, these lead to the use of minimal energy expenditure to execute movements with maximum efficiency.

The technique seeks to develop a state of constant alertness without losing communication with the environment; it is an invitation to explore, reflect, investigate and create through the body and its possibilities.

Workshop: “*Observation and painting*”

The experience of this **creative exploration** workshop sought to encourage group observation in relation to the phenomenon of “water.” The aim was to transfer the experience to the inner world, capture it through painting, and then share through conversation the individual and group reflections that emerge genuinely and spontaneously, thus creating *otros saberes* through unconventional paths. The selected painting technique was wet-on-wet watercolor.

Purpose

The purpose of the Encuentros, and for these 4 workshops, was to reflect and connect with the element of water from different perspectives, understanding that absolute and definitive truth is an illusion. During the event, we built a critical yet friendly space, capable of observing the world from different angles and navigating our convergences and disagreements, using the fluidity of water as an image that allows us to navigate new flows.

Contributions to the constestation

To begin with, the Encuentros, as a whole, gave visibility to the local conflicts around water and environment.

The workshops⁹ brought an opportunity for re-thinking in depth our research methodologies, thus propitiating new, diverse perspectives and destabilising the “traditional” ways we have to understand WATER, and beyond water, nature, environment and humanity.

There was a recognition of the contributions of a non-hegemonic Western science, the understandings unique to the Earth's various Indigenous peoples, and the insights the arts offer us to reimagine our relationship with the visible and invisible world around us. In this conception, knowledge is the product of collective (co)creation.

So are the experiences of contesting and reclaiming territories, as it was discussed and evidenced during the gathering, observing how different peoples and collectives build resistance and alternative ways of life in the face of multiple transgressions.

Further information:

[Video: Encuentros con el Agua.mov](#)

[Instagram:](#)

<https://www.instagram.com/encuentrosconelagua/>

Workshop: “Itrofill küme ko” (or The kindness of water in all its shapes”)

[9] Both those analysed here, and the others documented elsewhere

Buenos Aires workshop (credits: María de la Paz Toscani)

Tenants survey

Lead network node

IDRA, Barcelona, Spain. Asociación Civil por la Igualdad y la Justicia (ACIJ), Argentina. Habita65, Lisbon, Portugal. University of Chile, Santiago de Chile. University of Leeds, United Kingdom. Karlsruhe Institute of Technology, Germany. Universidad Autónoma de Madrid (UAM), Spain.

Participating actors

Representatives of the nodes: Faculty of Geography, University of Buenos Aires, Argentina. Centro de Estudios Urbanos y Regionales (CEUR), Argentina. Universidad Autónoma de Madrid, Spain. Universidad de la Laguna, Canary Islands, Spain. Basurama, Spain.

In Lisboa: Associação de Inquilinos Lisbonenses. Associação Solidariedade Imigrante. Associação Olho Vivo

Other representatives

In Barcelona: Activists, researchers, and housing experts who represent tenants and seek to improve their living conditions. These actors come from vulnerable backgrounds and are affected by the deregulation of the rental market.

Context of the project

The Encuesta Inquilina is a cross-cutting project of the CT network that has been built in recent years through the Urban Extractivism WG and the Territorial Accumulation WG. The aim of the initiative was to compare at an international level the reality of tenant households in different cities, involving the CT nodes from 6 different countries.

Rental markets are currently constituted as nodal spaces of contention, exploitation and resistance, where different agents, such as financial and real estate capital, the public sector, grassroots organisations and new trade unions, negotiate knowledge, money and rights, among others.

In Buenos Aires: Centro de Estudios Legales y Sociales (CELS). Escuela Interdisciplinaria de Altos Estudios (EIDAES). Frente de Organizaciones en Lucha (FOL). Frente Arde Rojo (FAR). Hábitat Sur. Corriente Villera Independiente. Centro para una Justicia Igualitaria y Popular (CEJIP). Barrio 31. La Boca Resiste y Propone. Consejerías de Vivienda

This is framed within a global context of progressive *tenantisation* of the population, the expansion of innovative forms of dispossession, as well as the formalisation of strategies of negotiation and social organisation.

In that sense, the Encuesta Inquilina is a line of research designed to respond to the specified CT objectives: documentation and categorisation of the logics and impacts of territorial accumulation, diagnosis of political mechanisms, mapping of territorial conflicts and analysis of the territoriality of politics. The survey consisted of data collection carried out by the tenants themselves, who have specific knowledge of the territory.

Within this framework, studies have been carried out on the conditions of the tenant households, which involved researchers from different nodes of the CT network, along with the participants. Throughout 2023 and 2024, six specific reports have been produced documenting the diagnoses of the rental situation in Barcelona, Lisbon, Madrid and Buenos Aires, and the diagnostic reports of the remaining cities involved are in the process of being produced.

Description of the cycle of the project

The initiative is structured through what we call a **scaffold workshop**:

- both the planning and the articulation amongst the different actors and countries involved were held through technical workshops (some in-person, some remote);
- afterwards, the design used a range of research methods and techniques (such as the design of the instrument of survey itself, interviews, documentary research, etc.), aiming to enhance the instrument but also to adjust it to the needs and requirements of each city and the participant actors.
- the implementation added some more technical workshops for the training component, and later on, the main community survey, and the data processing.
- the final step, the dissemination, is being carried out through different strategies, some in written (such as the reports mentioned above), audiovisual and digital formats, and some involving feedback meetings with the different communities involved. And there was also an international meeting to compare findings.

Among the myriad of activities of the Encuesta Inquilina, we focus here in two workshops: the one that took place in Buenos Aires (between October 2023 and April 2024) for training purposes, and the conference in Barcelona (1st and 2nd of July 2024) to comparatively analyse results of the tenant survey in different cities.

Buenos Aires survey (credits: María de la Paz Toscani)

In Buenos Aires

Location: popular neighbourhoods in the Metropolitan Area of Buenos Aires and housing estates in the City of Buenos Aires

Date: October 2023 - April 2024

Purpose

The purpose of Encuesta Inquilina was to identify common issues in renting in the different contexts and to work on proposals for possible legislative reform or public policies. The relational analysis also focused on how inequalities are generated between tenants and landlords.

Specifically, the objective of the Buenos Aires **scaffold workshop** was to coordinate with social organisations in the territories to implement the tenant survey in working class neighbourhoods in the Metropolitan area of Buenos Aires and in boarding houses and tenements in the City of Buenos Aires. It involved training the survey teams of the organisations, accompanying them in the survey and then returning the results.

Description of the activity

The Encuentro Internacional de Alquileres (International Encounter of Tenancy) in Buenos Aires has two local precedents in 2022 and 2023. On these occasions, the event proposed a national and multi-sectoral debate that, from different areas, provided information and proposals that contribute to the public debate and decision-making regarding rental policies at local, federal and national level. In 2024 the proposal was to scale up this meeting to an international level, promoting the dissemination of the results of the Encuesta already processed in the different nodes, and strategically promoting the reopening of the debate on the regulation of rents in the local context.

The Encuesta Inquilina provided training for the survey teams of the organisations involved, support during the data collection process, and later support on the critical interpretation of the results.

Training sessions were carried out with neighbourhood and social organisations so that their leaders - together with CT members of IGeo/UBA, CEUR and ACIJ - could carry out the survey in poor neighbourhoods and in boarding houses and tenements. The study was carried out through face-to-face surveys of tenants in slums and settlements in the Metropolitan area of Buenos Aires (households in the popular neighbourhoods of the Buenos Aires Metropolitan Area)

and room-renting in boarding houses and conventillos (boarding houses) in the City of Buenos Aires.

The community outreach activity included the previous training, the survey itself and then instances of discussion of the survey results.

In Barcelona

Location: IDRA, Barcelona

Date: 1st and 2nd of July, 2024

Purpose

The aim of the event in Barcelona was to analyse the results of the Encuesta Inquilina and discuss issues related to the deregulation of the rental market, tenant insecurity, and inequalities in rental relations in different cities (Barcelona, Madrid, Lisbon, Buenos Aires).

Barcelona International Technical Workshop (credits: Mónica Marion Cataño Otalora)

Description of the activity

The activity consisted of a two-day technical workshop at IDRA Barcelona, where representatives from different nodes (ACIJ, Lisbon, IDRA) participated. Reports were reviewed and common and specific problems of rental markets in Argentina, Spain and Portugal were discussed, to formulate preliminary proposals for future housing and rental policies.

During those two days, a participatory and comparative approach was used, combining data analysis with explanations of the historical context of each node to delve deeper into the reality of tenants in each city. The collective discussion allowed to develop a reflection on power relations in the rental market and to promote a relational vision that goes beyond conventional approaches. In addition, reports were reviewed and common and specific problems of rental markets in Argentina, Spain and Portugal were discussed, formulating and exploring preliminary proposals for future policies to improve the situation of tenants.

Outputs and contributions to the contestation

The Encuesta Inquilina refers to the exchange of knowledge and the production of policy recommendations that can be used in advocacy actions at local, national, regional and global levels. The return of the results to the communities involved, as well as the dissemination of lessons learned from the comparative analysis between nodes, are therefore fundamental aspects of the initiative.

In Buenos Aires, this activity made it possible to obtain information on the situation of tenant households in poor neighbourhoods and in boarding houses and tenements, a situation that has been little explored and for which no data is available. Likewise, the fact that the survey was carried out with representatives of the organisations made it possible, on the one hand, to train participants in this methodology and, at the same time, to produce information from the territories. The main results of these activities are the two reports on the situation of tenant households in both of the urban contexts explored. Complementarily, the information collected by a variety of media in the different contexts also served as an instrument to fight for the right to decent housing, in the context of the parliamentary debate that sought to repeal the Rent Law in Argentina during 2023.

Two reports were prepared about tenant households in popular neighbourhoods of the Metropolitan Area of Buenos Aires (AMBA) and of tenants in hotels, guesthouses and tenements in the Autonomous City of Buenos Aires (CABA).

In Barcelona, issues such as the lack of protection for tenants, economic pressure and discrimination in access to housing were discussed. Participants identified the need to reorder existing data and collect information on income and rent distribution to analyse the equity gap between tenants and landlords.

The initiative contributed to the contestation by providing a space to question the dominant narrative of supply and demand in the rental market, elaborating a critique on how these dynamics perpetuate structural inequalities. Participants generated policy proposals to resist tenants' lack of protection, highlighting the urgency of regulating the market to guarantee the right to housing.

The contestation in this case is understood as the collective action of questioning and challenging the deregulatory practices that harm tenants. It is a process of resistance that seeks to make visible the injustices in the rental market and to mobilise structural changes in housing policies.

Materials for training workshops in Buenos Aires

The workshop allowed participants to deepen their understanding of the dynamics of the rental market in different cities and the effects of deregulation on the daily lives of tenants. The experience promoted an exchange of knowledge on the situation of tenants, highlighting the similarities and particularities in each context and emphasising the importance of an international and comparative perspective to address housing issues. In terms of the network, the common framework of the Tenancy Survey methodology was deepened, and the activity also presents an opportunity to expand this type of analysis to other cities with similar problems.

The data generated thanks to the commitment and synergy between social movements and researchers of the CT network reinforces the impact that the Tenant Survey has had on the public debate, as well as on the articulation of a critical study aimed at intervention on the rental market.

The initiative generated a return to the communities by communicating the data through audiovisual formats to amplify its impact and dissemination, and to generate networking spaces to share the final results, as a way of closing the project. The videos, through a format of tenant narratives based on lived experience, will not only serve to train the members of the associations themselves, but will also have an amplifying effect on the impact and functions of the organisations involved, in reclaiming the right to housing and the city, also through artistic methods, such as performance and visuals.

Further information:

Reports

[Encuesta inquilina archivos – Contested TERRITORIES](#)

[De propietarios a inquilinos. Informe sobre la creciente desigualdad en el acceso a la propiedad](#)

[Encuesta inquilina 2024: alquilar en el AMBA en tiempos de libre mercado – ACIJ](#)

[Publicaciones – IDRA Instituto de Investigación Urbana de Barcelona](#)

Blog

[Avances en la investigación sobre la Encuesta Inquilina – Contested TERRITORIES](#)

Video

[La Encuesta Inquilina - y su dimensión metodológica](#)

Buenos Aires survey (credits: María de la Paz Toscani)

Encuentro Metodologías Otras: Territorial disputes, dialogue of knowledges and futures, a space for exchange

Lead network node

UCHILE

Participating actors

Representatives of the nodes: Universidad de la Frontera – UFRO, Chile. Nodo Bolivia.

Other representatives: Centro Cultural Espacio Matta, La Granja, Ruka Ranguínelwe, Parque O'Higgins, ONG Investiga Colina, Fundación Ojos de Mar, Asociación Calaucán, Postgraduate School FAU – UCHILE and Direction of Extension and Liaison FAU – UCHILE

Context of the activities

A six-day gathering focused on exchanging and reflecting on alternative research, practices, and collaborative methodologies that explore elements of community-based knowledge, drawing from decolonial, feminist perspectives and indigenous methodologies: this is, the challenge of designing and sustaining otros haceres (other methodologies and practices) intertwined with the co-production and revitalisation of otros saberes.

Territories are made up of multiple dimensions. They are traversed by relationships mediated by disputes. Soils, waters, horizons, energies, and the interweaving of nature-cultures shape the ways in which communities imagine and construct their spaces. Identifying and representing these disputes is a challenge for social analysis in the face of conditions of instability, fluidity, and unpredictability in today's worlds.

Research methods play a central role in producing the reality we observe; they help bring to light the diverse imaginations and desires about our presents and futures. Therefore, these methods are not naive to the realities we propose to analyse.

The gathering took as its starting point this guiding principle: territorial research methods must have the capacity to relate and connect dynamics and processes that traditional methods struggle to achieve, overcoming research practices that observe the social by fragmenting phenomena into social fields—work, care, festivities, etc.—. The territory links all of them, weaving, connecting, and interweaving.

Timeframe

Santiago de Chile, 17 to 22 April, 2024

Territory

Chile

Santiago de Chile

The Encounter had 4 goals:

1. to promote the exchange between territorial research projects,
2. to learn about the realities of territories in contestation, jointly thinking about alternative narratives about the conflict, incorporating our experiences in a cooperative manner,
3. to explore dynamics of knowledge exchange between people and associations that critically reflect on models of creation of and with "other" knowledge and wisdom and
4. to explore the affective, emotional and embodied dimensions of the ways in which people and communities experience their territories.

In order to reach them, the leading Node proposed three cores to organise the activities:

- **Explorar (Explore)**
- **Expandir (Spread)**
- **Narrar (Narrate)**

Description of the event

During the first two days, and after the welcome reception, it was time for the first core.

- **Explorar (Explore)**

There were four workshops

1. **Exploring the movement as a promoter of social change, by José Vidal.**

This **creative exploration workshop** intended to work on the connection with one's own body and communicating with others through it and within space, with the aim of breaking down barriers and limits to rethink how we relate and think in our daily lives.

It appealed to movement and play, as a means to enable bodies, touch, laughter, gaze, attention, and even error or the unexpected to emerge and open the possibility of creating something different, a door to the possibility of something else appearing, another alternative, a seed with potential, from every gesture, every idea, every direction.

2. Exploring Filmic celluloid as support for creation by Colectivo de Experimentación e Investigación en Formato Fílmico. CEIS8

Although deploying and sharing a series of technical skills, we consider this workshop in essence a **creative exploration** one, since it was developed under the premise of "the concern for keeping celluloid creation active (...) not responding to a nostalgic or fetishistic recovery, but rather to a current artistic practice that has taken a new place in the face of the norm imposed by digital production".¹⁰

This language and this format become, thus conceived, a contested territory in itself, "a vehicle for critical and aesthetic reflection aware of its territoriality and as a collective creation capable of expressing geographical, political and cultural diversity".

3. Social cartography: body, territory and good living workshop

With the purpose to know and apply a participatory and mapping methodology to capture aspects of social realities that are not easily explored through other methodologies, this body-territory workshop sought to work in the intersection of geography, art, literature, photography, and film to enrich academic investigation processes and to be able to co-create knowledge with the communities of the territories under analysis.

Through practical exercises and theoretical reflections, the workshop proposed to explore social cartography as a tool for finding the threads linking body and territory, and understand how this relationship influences individual and collective well-being, promoting forms of coexistence that aim to consider other possible territories.

4. Guided visit to Centro Cultural Espacio Matta

This **technical workshop** explored the history of the Cultural Centre, starting with in 1971 with the creation of the mural "*El primer gol del Pueblo chileno*" (The First Goal of the Chilean People) by Roberto Matta in conjunction with the Ramona Parra Brigade, painted in commemoration of the first anniversary of Salvador Allende's government, totally covered afterwards by Pinochet Dictatorship's authorities in an attempt for censoring -or destroying- it, and "(re)dis-covered" years later with the return of Democracy.

On the third day, the focus changed into:

- **Expandir** (Spread- Expand)

With this frame of work, there was a kaleidoscopic activity: a technical workshop for the presentation of research projects, but in an "open bazaar" or methodologies fair format. It was its purpose to create a non-formal space that would favour dialogue, conversation and collaboration between researchers working on different topics but all involving non-conventional research methodologies, opening up to the community and all those who have an interest.

Lastly, the two remaining days of the *Encuentro* were dedicated to the third core:

- **Narrar** (Narrate)

There were three workshops planned to enhance the participants' abilities and skills for telling, emphasising on the generation of conceptual and empirical knowledge about territorial inequalities. Two of them had the form of territorial visits, aiming to learn about two realities very close to Santiago, and together, consider alternative narratives about the conflict, incorporating our experiences cooperatively.

At the workshop "Exploring Filmic celluloid as support for creation" by CEIS8

[10] From the Programme of activities, available here: https://www.contested-territories.net/wp-content/uploads/2024/06/chile2024-ProgramaEncuentro_COMPRIMIDO.pdf

1. Following in the footsteps of extractivism: dialogues and reflections on peri-urban territorial conflicts in Colina. Invited and guided by: NGO Investiga Colina

This body-territory workshop focused on exploring and experiencing the impacts of extractivism in the commune of Colina. Guided by the NGO members through three stops, the participants identified experienced first handed the effects of extractivism in the people, the landscape and the environment, as well as the commons and collectives struggling in contestation to these processes

2. Visit to the wetlands Ojos de Mar. Invited and guided by Ojos de Mar Foundation

An emblematic site of socio-environmental conflict, Ojos de Mar in Lolleo San Antonio, was the chosen place for this **body-territory workshop**. Here, the participants learned about the long, multiscalar, strategic struggle of the community, explored the political, legal and social scopes of the conflict, and the non less multi-strategic manners the contestation acquired through years.

3. Exercising new/ alternative narratives

At the conclusion of the event, two different moments of evaluation and sharing took place: this technical workshop was the second one, after the main "senti-pensante" evaluation, aimed to bring into action the lessons learnt by doing. Turning the new knowledge into otros haceres.

The participants, divided in 4 groups, had the challenge to transform the previous evaluation moment into a collective reflection in both text and image, departing from the personal lived experience, and further co-creating a collective text with the illustrative image, and finally sharing in a plenary session the creation.

Contributions to the contestation

In the case of this node, contestation is understood as the organized ways of defending places under threat -particularly bodies of water- through formal mechanisms provided for by law. But above all, the organizations' work is based on disseminating information and generating emotional ties between affected populations and threatened places.

One of the contributions of this encounter was to raise awareness on the gendered impacts of territorial conflicts: the methodological processes used are strongly influenced by feminist and community-based feminist perspectives.

In particular, initiatives focused on women's experiences and territories were presented at the Project Fair, such as the work of Maritorias (working with women shore gatherers in Chiloe), Chungungas (women living along the seashore), and Menstrual Territories (the relationship between young women and their menstruation and everyday territorialities). These projects were highly appreciated by fair visitors for presenting little-known and unconventional themes and methods that reveal the invisible experiences of women in the production, reclaiming, and imagining of territory.

Additionally, as a result of the event, a collaborative network was generated, with concrete collaborations and a special issue on the way. Above all, the possibility of networking, connecting initiatives and interests taking place in different parts of the country. The need arose to connect more strongly collaborative research and experiences based on other methodologies and to achieve their academic legitimisation, for which this encounter was a very important step.

At the "Social cartography: body, territory and good living" workshop

Further information:

Programme

https://www.contested-territories.net/wp-content/uploads/2024/06/chile2024-ProgramaEncuentro_COMPRIMIDO.pdf

Instagram

https://www.instagram.com/p/C4dkgrPomNt/?img_index=1

Video

[ENCUENTRO METODOLOGIAS OTRAS 2024](#)

Blog

["Metodologías otras" - DISPUTAS TERRITORIALES, DIÁLOGO DE SABERES Y FUTUROS – Contested TERRITORIES](#)

Urban Prefigurations

Lead network node

Newcastle University, United Kingdom

Participating actors

Representatives of the nodes: University of Chile. University of Buenos Aires (Geography Department), Argentina. Torero Films, Spain

Other representatives: Ciudad Futura (Rosario, Argentina), Ukamau (Santiago de Chile), and Brigadas Populares (Belo Horizonte, Brasil). Diverse community leaders and experts from Argentina, Brazil and Chile

Context of the activities

Urban Prefigurations is the name of a project within the CONTESTED_TERRITORY Network working group on policy mobilities. Its main aim is to document the experience of social movements and communities in engaging in social innovation practices.

The initiative is based on critical territorial visits carried out in 2022 and 2023, where interviews with social movements, political groups, communities and residents were conducted, complemented by the analysis of archive material. The filming of the audiovisual material with the participating communities took place in May 2024 (Nuevo Alberdi, Rosario, Argentina), July 2024 (Maestranza Ukamau, Santiago de Chile, Chile), August 2024 (Ocupação Vitória, Belo Horizonte, Brazil).

The title of the project also gives the name to a digital platform, currently under development, where audiovisual material will be available for the dissemination of community knowledge. The digital platform will also present a web series (10 mini-episodes of 5 minutes each) detailing practices of the movements of three case studies, capturing experiences of social movements, community leaders and experts from Argentina, Brazil and Chile, and, at a later stage, also a feature film.

At the core of this work are conflictual and insurgent practices that challenge the commodification of urban life and space. These include anti-eviction campaigns that resist displacement, grassroots mobilisations that have successfully pushed for ordinances banning the construction of private gated neighbourhoods, and collective processes for co-producing neighbourhood masterplans that reflect the lived priorities of residents rather than speculative interests.

Timeframe

May 2024 (Nuevo Alberdi, Rosario, Argentina), July 2024 (Maestranza Ukamau, Santiago de Chile, Chile), August 2024 (Ocupação Vitória, Belo Horizonte, Brazil)

Community allotment, Vitória occupation, Belo Horizonte

Territory

The original idea to develop a municipalist platform for documenting diverse forms of knowledge came from a social movement, and the proposal to create audiovisual material for each experience was jointly developed by the Contested Territories nodes of Newcastle University, University of Chile, University of Buenos Aires (Geography Department), with the same movement that conceived the initiative.

This project seeks to give continuity to and conclude the line of work of the Working Group of Policy Mobilities - policy and knowledge circulation, which was born as a sub-working group in 2020 within the Working Group of Critical Policy Analysis. More specifically, it focuses on work on the circulation of counter-hegemonic knowledge and alternative practices of inclusive territorial development linked to the new municipalism movement.

Description of the activity

Urban Prefigurations is the name of the WG Policy Mobilities' mini-project documenting the experience of social movements and communities which produce social innovation and bottom-up knowledge, and it is structured through what we denominate **scaffold workshop**. In this case, different ongoing projects of the CT network were intertwined through a workshop that gave origin and helped in planning the mini-project. The next instance was the design of the platform and the production of the docuseries, with all the necessary tasks for that, which are not workshops in themselves. Through the length of the project, workshops were held either with technical or logistics purposes, sustaining the whole process.

Following the engagement with various social movements in Argentina, Brazil and Chile, it was decided to develop a digital platform to collect and disseminate this knowledge. The innovations that these practices generate are the focus of the video interviews that form the basis for the docuseries. All innovations have in common proposals for more democratic and inclusive territorial development that were produced by community actors operating outside formal institutions. All the movements were contacted to confirm their support and filming began in 2024. Before each visit, the theme of the interviews, the questionnaire, the profile of the participants and the format of the episodes were jointly defined. Each edited episode was shared with the movements for their input and subsequent conclusion.

Each video interview with residents, community leaders and social movement representatives aims to describe how they make important changes in the life of their neighbourhoods. The final results -in the form of a digital platform, webseries and feature film- are intended as a form of dissemination for community learning, enabling social movements and actors from different cities to share their knowledge and connect with other groups.

Description of the activity

Urban Prefigurations foregrounds community knowledge that emerges directly from the experience of movements and communities in their struggle for the right to the city. Knowledge generated by these communities is directly related to their practices to advance in the defence and improvement of local territories.

Replicability is also a main focus of the Urban Prefigurations project. Through documenting different activities in a docuseries, the aim is to disseminate community-based thought and related practices via a platform geared to interested movements, activists and researchers based in other territorial settings.

Outputs and contributions to the contestation

Three main products of this collaborative work are presented as a result:

1. Digital platform "Urban Prefigurations", to be continuously updated beyond the end of CT project (launched: January 2025);
2. Docuserie "Urban Prefigurations - Popular Planning" (10 mini-episodes): the series will offer 10 short films on strategies and tools for territorial community development based on case experiences. It will be accessible in language and format, and oriented to other civil society organisations and activists (over the course of 2025);
3. Feature film (title to be defined): it will focus on the right to the city in Latin American cities and the role of civil society organisations in devising and implementing alternative strategies for inclusive social and spatial development. It will be aimed at the general public and for educational use (July 2025).

The contribution of the initiative to contestation is fostering a systemic change in the way neoliberal capitalism produces unequal urban lives and spaces: this translates into documenting and visualising this territorial dispute, and understanding and disseminating alternative approaches to sustainable and inclusive territorial development. For instance, in many of the documented experiences, these are neighbourhoods where eviction processes are underway.

In addition, the initiative facilitates the exchange of knowledge and experiences, to strengthen and develop an ecosystem of municipalist policies and instruments.

Interview with residents, Vitória occupation, Belo Horizonte

Further information:

[Collaborative platform: urbanpref.com](http://urbanpref.com)
[Instagram: Urban Pref \(@urbanpref\)](https://www.instagram.com/urbanpref/) •
[Instagram photos and videos](#)

International Seminar Touristification and commodification of Nature. Debates and proposals

Lead network node

Universidad de La Laguna, Canarias, Spain (coordinator). Universidad de Buenos Aires (FAUBA), Argentina. CEUR-CONICET, Argentina. Universidad Autónoma de Madrid, Spain. Left Hand Rotation, Spain. Habita65, Portugal

Participating actors

Representatives of the nodes: Universidad de Chile. Universidad de la Frontera, Chile. PUCJ Cali, Colombia. Facultad de Antropología, University of Buenos Aires, Argentina. Politecnico of Milan, Italia. University of Sheffield, United Kingdom. Basurama, Spain. CEUR-CONICET, Argentina. Ciudades Reveladas. Flacso, Ecuador and CEPLAG/IIADI, Bolivia

Other representatives:

Academic institutions: University of the Balearic Islands, the Canary Islands Institute of Agrarian Sciences and the Iriarte School of Tourism.

Ecosocial collectives: Asociación Tinerfeña de Amigos por la Naturaleza, Salvar La Tejita, Salvar El Puertito, Canarias Pa'Lante, Fundación Canarina, Fundación Telesforo Bravo - Juan Coello, Environmental Department of La Orotava's City Council

Context of the activity

The seminar "Touristification and Commodification of Nature. Debates and Proposals" brought together national and international experts to reflect on the processes of appropriation of nature by tourism initiatives, which generate situations of social inequality and stress on the environment. The initiative, coordinated by Universidad de La Laguna, with the participation of several other nodes of the Contested Territories network, started a debate between environmental groups, social movements, artists, and academic researchers from different institutions.

This initiative, carried out in Tenerife, arose in response to the recent and intense protests that happened in April 2024 (and also a few days after the end of the seminar) in the Canary Islands, against the processes of touristification and commodification of nature.¹¹

Timeframe

From 23 to 25 October 2024 at La Laguna University (Tenerife, Spain)

Seminar participants at El Rincón (La Orotava)

Following the input of several working groups of the Contested Territories network in different regions of Latin America and Europe, the initiative offered a space for dialogue on these topics. It was part of a participatory process called "Canarias pa'lante" and its aim was to present different perspectives not only from the Contested Territories network, but also from social collectives, artists and researchers.

Organised in different venues on the island of Tenerife, the activity took different formats such as debates, talks, presentation of case studies (in presence, online and hybrid modalities). The activity was structured around different axes that addressed some key aspects of the topic of touristification and involved the different collectives in the co-production of the event.

[11] See, for instance [CANARIAS: MANIFESTACIONES multitudinarias contra la "MASIFICACIÓN" TURÍSTICA | RTVE Noticias](#) or [CANARIAS: Una MANIFESTACIÓN contra el TURISMO MASIVO une a las SIETE ISLAS del ARCHIPIÉLAGO | RTVE](#) or [Las protestas vuelven a recorrer el archipiélago canario para pedir un turismo más sostenible: "Canarias tiene un límite"](#)

The seminar was organized into:

- talks and presentations on case studies;
- audiovisual productions;
- and sites explorations (that we describe below);

Description of the activity

As part of the fieldwork, participants went on a visit to a site symbolic of the struggle to defend the territory: El Rincón (La Orotava) with presentations from social and environmental groups and speakers (Ben Magec – Ecologists in Action, El Rincón Coordinator, Save La Tejita Platform, Save El Puertito Platform, ATAN, Canarias Pa'lante).

The aim of this **body-territory workshop** was to present diverse perspectives on the processes of touristification and the commodification of nature, but most particularly, to have a lived experience of the territory, the nature and the landscape, putting the body and the senses in interaction with the site, while fostering dialogue with social collectives.

The participant environmental groups have been struggling against the effects of touristification and commodification of nature, and this joint activity with CT members sought also to put forward holistic proposals for action.

Outputs and contributions to the contestation:

One of the key contributions of the initiative was its ability to foster a meaningful exchange between academic actors and collectives engaged in environmental and social struggles. This collaboration extended beyond academic boundaries and enabled the strengthening of ties with organisations actively involved in resistance processes, including both community members and technical experts. The field excursion and related debates served as particularly rich moments of co-learning, where new forms of protest and potential topics for future audiovisual productions were identified.

Environmental issues emerged as a central element in the articulation of contestation, particularly in geographically constrained and ecologically vulnerable spaces like the Canary Islands. Contestation cannot be understood only as street demonstrations, but can be translated into diverse and creative forms, such as the production of audiovisual materials.

These tools are powerful and promising, especially given the diffusion of stereotypical imaginaries connected to the landscape of the Canary Islands. In this context, the creation of counter-audiovisual narratives can serve to challenge dominant representations, give voice to dispossessed communities, and highlight their forms of resistance.

These alternative narratives help to broaden the understanding of contestation itself—not only as protest in the public sphere, but also as strategic communication, symbolic action, and knowledge production.

The initiative also contributed to the ongoing participatory process '*Canarias Pa'lante*', which emerged from the April 20th demonstrations in the Canary Islands, and helped to articulate a collective critique of the commodification of nature, as well as other related transformation processes in housing and public coastal spaces, and to develop responses grounded in local contexts.

A significant conceptual output of this work is the debate on the idea of nature. Rather than seeing nature merely through the lens of scarcity and protection, in the context of the workshop nature was understood as a non-human entity deeply intertwined with social reproduction—an appropriated and appropriable space which can be a guarantor of enjoyment, of non-urbanisation or of its degradation.

This view becomes especially meaningful in the insular context of the Canary Islands, where geographic limits redefine the context of these non-human natures and provide a political scale for imagining emancipatory processes—what some frame as the *right to the island*.

The exchange beyond academia allowed to strengthen ties between organizations that carry out resistance processes and technical experts, the initiative generated new knowledge, built networks of solidarity, and expanded the repertoire of resistance.

Further information:

[Programme: Programacion.pdf](#)

International Seminar's banner.

International Symposium: Coexistences and Struggles for the Inhabited Space

Lead network node

Pontificia Universidad Javeriana Cali, Colombia

Participating actors

Representatives of the nodes: University of Newcastle, United Kingdom. University of Sheffield, United Kingdom. University of Leeds, United Kingdom. Instituto de Investigación y Acción para el Desarrollo Integral - IIADI, Bolivia.

Other representatives: Communication Law Research Seminar of the Pontificia Universidad Javeriana Cali. Gobernación del Valle del Cauca. Monkox Chiquitano People, Santa Cruz, Bolivia. Habitancia de Aguablanca network. Asomevid (Asociación Mejorando Vidas). Embera Chamí, community of the Guasiruma reserve. Trans women members of Transmujer. Institución Educativa Nuevo Latir, Aguablanca. Fundación Son de mi Gente, Aguablanca, Trono Theatre group, from Bolivia.

Timeframe

From 19 to 22 March, 2024. Cali, Colombia

Context of the event

The initiative was made of different workshops which took place in March 2024 at the Pontificia Universidad Javeriana in Cali, in the Aguablanca District, in the city centre of Cali, in the indigenous reserve Wasiruma, in the rural area of the municipality of Vijes in Cauca Valley.

The Symposium set the scene for an exchange between academics from the CONTESTED_TERRITORY network and social representatives from Bolivia, Chile, Ecuador and Colombia, through an itinerant event with communities in south-western Colombia, in order to reflect on the social practices of youth, indigenous, Afro-descendant and LGBTQ+ communities concerning the assimilation and the resistance to processes of Territorial Accumulation (TA).

The aim was to develop a collaborative experience in dialogue with Latin American popular knowledge, to make visible existing practices of innovation and to generate alternative knowledge on the polysemy of Territorial Accumulation.

This took the form of itinerant meetings - walking reflections with communities, groups and collectives active in urban and rural contexts of Valle del Cauca, for the discussion of possible coexistence in the framework of social struggles for the inhabited space-, and a series of podcasts, aimed at the cross-cultural comparison and dissemination of the organisational and research experiences managed by the event's participants.

The symposium arises from the demands for cultural recognition, economic redistribution, political representation and participation, and environmental justice in different communities (Aguablanca district, centre of Cali, Guasiruma Indigenous Resguardo, Valle del Cauca). Cisgender women, trans women, indigenous communities and Afro-descendant communities construct distinct forms of a moral grammar of social conflict. While certain dimensions of their actions are shaped by specific cultural

struggles a comparative perspective that emerges through the traversal of their territories reveals striking commonalities in their demands—particularly those concerning water quality, the right to safe mobility within their lands, and the remediation of environmental degradation, among others. These series of material demands are, transversally, claims from the inhabited space.

Son de mi Gente, from Aguablanca and Trono group, from El Alto (Bolivia) together at the Symposium

Description of the activities

The communities were actively involved in organising the activities, and agreements were reached to allow passage through their territories. Meetings and group interviews were useful tools to understand community perspectives. The routes were planned with attention to issues of territorial accumulation. Both urban and rural contexts were addressed, focusing on conflicts related to territorial use.

The five-day meeting was aimed at developing a walking dialogue across communities in Valle del Cauca, enabling the “learning by walking” or “learning with the body” through an academic and experience-based resource.

The first day began with a ceremony facilitated by Windsor Torrico (Bolivia node). There was a space where two books were socialised.¹²

The **technical workshop**: “Production of podcasts” was developed with the objective of enhancing narrative skills of social struggling groups through oral products. And to actually produce one podcast to narrate the intertwined struggles of diverse communities and collectives in Latin America, facilitated through CONTESTED_TERRITORY network.

The musical “*Dónde meter la cabeza*” was presented, an artistic work by children from the Marroquín II neighbourhood in which they narrate the history of the neighbourhood at the end of the 20th century and the urban conflicts of the beginning of the 21st century.¹³

The second day’s activities included a series of talks and presentations of leadership experiences of LGTBIQ+ activists and transgender women who participate in political processes related to the claims of sexual rights and the use of public space in Cauca Valley.

In the afternoon, the last activity was a “Reflexión caminada” (walking reflection): a **body-territory workshop** going all over the Centre of Cali with the guidance of Pamela Montaña, from Fundación Transmujer, who facilitated the observation and experiencing of the city with a gender perspective.

On the third day, the walks and exchange of knowledge in the territories continued with visit to the experience of ecotourism and recovery of Charco Azul Lagoon. Then a meeting with the organisations part of the Habitancia network -an association for social innovation and peace building in Aguablanca. where the concept of *Habitancia* was discussed and nurtured with the contributions of the participants. And the end of the day was marked by the **body-territory workshop** or “reflexión caminada” through Bulevar de Oriente, a project that recreates a platform for living and restoring public space based on new ecologies. The soil, water, air, sun, flora, and fauna, along with recreational, leisure, cultural, and educational activities, and agro-ecosystems, create a system that connects people, providing experiences that build a culture of environmental belonging within the community. Floodable gardens capture the memory of water through temporary landscapes; the Bulevar del Oriente is a platform that enables the transformation of a community by empowering and recognising its cultural values.

The crew of “Dónde meter la cabeza” Opera-salsa, with members of CT network

[12] The first book entitled: ‘Nuestras Luchas Cuentan’ (Our Struggles Count), which describes the struggles of young indigenous women in Santa Cruz (Bolivia) narrated through oral histories and photographs taken by youth activists.

And the second book was entitled ‘Peace in Aguablanca’, and presents territorial peace processes in low-income neighbourhoods in eastern Cali. Paz en Aguablanca. Aproximaciones

[13] See the full documentation on Section 2: Performances, below

CT network researchers at work

Fresneda, in the municipality of Vijes, a rural area of Valle del Cauca. The participants were received and sustained a fruitful dialogue with the leaders of the community, discussing similarities and particularities of the processes of territorial accumulation and contestation. The last activity was the third **body-territory workshop** of the day: a “Reflexión caminada” through Calima, Darien.

On the fifth and last day, a podcast was recorded to reflect on the experience of situated dialogues.

Outputs and contributions to the contestation

The main output of the symposium was a series of territorially situated exchanges based on dialogues of knowledge that embrace difference and horizontality between actors.

Indeed, the event contributed to the discussion of bottom-up initiatives related to cultural, economic, and political innovation, as well as the visibility of traditional knowledge and practices, which address the consequences of territorial exploitation, displacement, and the commodification of the environment and nature.

The technical workshops favoured the exchange of knowledge on how territorial accumulation processes lead to assimilation or resistance practices in the contexts of Bolivia, Chile, Ecuador and Colombia.

In the itinerant events, participants learned from community experiences of public deliberation and social protest against territorial accumulation in Colombia. This meeting was attended by Afro-descendant urban communities and organisations, the population of an indigenous reserve and representatives of sexual and gender diversity collectives.

Overall, the event promoted co-creation, participatory analysis and public dissemination of knowledge. For this reason, narrative methodologies -such as co-creation of a podcast- were deployed to compare and contrast experiences of territorial reclamation based on ancestral, popular or dissident knowledge.

The activities were structured with expressive exercises that allowed participants to learn about the history of their territories. Particularly, the performative experiences sought to demonstrate the impact of the externalities caused by the inadequacies of the state in addressing the crises caused by violence and the dispossession of the rights of these communities. This is the case with *Dónde Meter la Cabeza* (Where to Put Your Head) and the exchange generated with the Trono group. They were able to share insights that challenge the order of injustices occurring in Cali and El Alto.

The contestations refer to performative experiences that seek to demonstrate the impact of externalities caused by injustices. The Symposium achieved to present Colombian experiences that have made dialogue possible with State entities that have found their territorial claims justifiable. Such processes contribute to the study of how ancestral, popular, and dissident knowledge can influence the deliberative scenarios provided by the State.

Further information:

Programme

[Marzo 19,22. 2024_compressed \(1\) - Carlos Tobar.pdf](#)

Blog

[Realizamos el simposio internacional: Convivencias y luchas por el espacio habitado en Cali, Colombia – Contested TERRITORIES](#)

Instagram

[Secretaría de Equidad Valle | En la @gobvalle creemos en la importancia de la diversidad y la inclusión. La Administración departamental hizo parte de las jornadas del... | Instagram](#)

Podcast

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=VPXIAgeK9UU&list=PLTMiKIYnU5HIDOfL4GY2Ct55PNhGek1jC&index=3>

Food as a Field of Contest: Alternatives in Production and Marketing as Practices of Resistance in Berlin, Madrid, and Buenos Aires

Berlin Audiovisual Summer School workshop

Lead network nodes

Faculty of Agronomy, University of Buenos Aires, Argentina. CONICET-CEUR, Argentina. Torero Film, Spain

Participating actors

Other representatives: Family, eco, and organic farmers, producers and fair-marchants

Context of the event

This research project was derived from the Berlin Summer Audiovisual School (2022) and the Audiovisual Laboratory of Madrid (2024), which gave it structure as a scaffold workshop.

The aim of this School was to invite CT researchers to experiment with different methodologies outside of their usual academic work and backgrounds, encouraging them to acquire and put into practice new narrating skills and languages. It focused both on practical exercises -learning by doing- as in theoretical sessions, with the expectations of concrete audiovisual products as its outputs and being followed by experimental art events, performance presentations, etc.

The training in Berlin lasted 5 weeks: it involved **technical and creative exploration workshops**, field visits, and consulting sessions for the participants' audiovisual projects.

The participants (from more than 5 different countries and nodes) got the opportunity to familiarize themselves with the technical aspects of audiovisual media; dramaturgy and aesthetics of audiovisual media (and performance),

Timeframe

From 2022 to 2025 in Berlin (Germany), Madrid (Spain) and Buenos Aires (Argentina)

including the approaches and distinct narrative styles of each filmmaker and each genre; analysing the different formats at existing levels (YouTube, Facebook, WhatsApp, Twitter, TikTok, etc.), and approaching "new" audiovisual techniques.

The second part of this training initiative took place in Madrid, and convened 24 researchers from Argentina, Bolivia, Colombia, Chile, United Kingdom and Portugal: with a duration of 10 days it was focused on carrying out, producing and editing audiovisual works derived from ongoing research and social intervention processes in different territories.

Image depicting the filming process in Berlin

Description of the project

This initiative comes from a cooperation between the Faculty of Agronomy of UBA and the CEUR (Argentina) with the purpose of exploring the construction and implementation of alternative forms of food production and marketing, in a comparative analysis of Latin American and European markets. The selection of experiences for the trilogy took into account those that problematize the human-nature relationship, as well as the economic logics promoted by neoliberalism, confronting them with alternative meanings and practices, interpreting these as forms of resistance and contestation to the hegemonic model.

In the course of the initial workshop in Berlin Summer School, the team drew the general programme of research and consulted it with the director and colleagues. While the shootings of the German and Spanish experiences were held simultaneously with the respective training workshops, the Buenos Aires one took place after the end of the course.

Through a series of interviews, the audiovisual trilogy recovers the practices and perspectives of agroecological producers, consumers, members of consumer cooperatives, fairgoers, among others. Among the myriad of perspectives, emerged the hegemonic and counter-hegemonic meanings of what is considered environmentally sustainable production vis-à-vis different ways of interpreting and implementing the economic exchange of food. For example, the European Union's definitions of what constitutes environmentally sustainable production are valued and challenged, for instance, the forms of commercialization carried out by supermarkets - which involve exploitative labor relations and/or long-distance transportation of food, with the resulting carbon footprint-

These definitions and practices are thus challenged by other actors who observe that the label of "ecological" cannot be restricted to the controlled/reduced use of industrial inputs but must also consider local products and/or labor relations and/or forms of social and solidarity economy.

Hence, greenwashing is problematized, and environmental and health issues are reintroduced into food production as objects of dispute.

The method used was audiovisual production, which surveyed interviews and practices, seeking to capture the meaning created -consciously and/or unconsciously, individually or collectively- by the participants. The observation captured through the camera resulted in a powerful resource for visualizing and highlighting every day and collective practices that are not always recovered and/or valued in discourse.

The Trilogy premiere took place during the 5th Ciudades Reveladas Festival, in Madrid (May-June 2025), contributing with the objectives of the Audiovisual School and Lab towards collective visualisations and debates of the products.

Image depicting the filming process in Berlin

Contributions to the contestation

Regarding the training workshops directed by Torero during both the Summer School and the Lab, the new abilities and skills acquired by the researchers allowed them to explore new languages and supports, and consequently, new approaches to the perspectives, ideas, and meanings of the communities they work with, thus multiplying and enhancing the visibility of their resistance and disputes.

Specifically speaking, the CEUR-FAUBA team project, through the documentary audiovisual trilogy, restores the production and marketing of "alternative" foods as a space for dispute and makes it possible to denaturalize some categories of classification of these practices by government entities, which are presented as neutral and/or technical -"agroecological", "bio", etc-.

By contesting these alleged natural categories, the trilogy makes evident their political nature insofar as they are functional and/or promote market logic and with them the forms of organization and social hierarchy that derive from the neoliberal model. The documented alternative practices can reveal other ways of thinking about and producing the world.

Image depicting the filming process in Buenos Aires

The actors interviewed or surveyed about their practices often interpret the significance of producing, marketing, and consuming organic food as not limited to environmental conservation or ensuring good health. In this way, they also strive to build another world, another economy, other labor relations, etc, which is a means of contestation by imagining the territories and alternative, counter-hegemonic ways to inhabit them.

Contestation is, therefore, not only a form of resistance to the neoliberal model, in terms of stopping it and/or preventing its expansion/implementation, but also in the construction of alternative forms of production and social organization. It is a creative activity that seeks to produce alternative, more inclusive and just forms of life.

Workshop at the Audiovisual Laboratory of Madrid

Further information:

Berlin Audiovisual Summer School

<https://escueladeveranoberlin.blogspot.com/>

Madrid LabAV

<https://labavmadrid.blogspot.com/2024/05/blog-post.html>

The documentary trilogy

[Lo bio, eco y agro en Alimentos y Sentidos Ecológicos: Trilogía documental – Contested TERRITORIES](#)

In Youtube

[Lo bio en Berlín](#)

[Lo eco en Madrid](#)

[Lo AgroEco en Buenos Aires, Argentina entrega](#)

Instagram

https://www.instagram.com/p/DL0C3k1xjZw/?img_index=1

Biochar Filters for communities affected by urban contamination in the Katari Basin, Bolivia

Lead network node

Instituto de Investigación y Acción para El Desarrollo Integral -IIADI, Bolivia

Participating actors

Representatives of the nodes: University of Sheffield, United Kingdom. University of Newcastle, United Kingdom

Context of the activities

The indigenous communities living in the rural area of the Katari River have been deeply affected by severe river pollution in recent decades. This has impacted their health and economic well-being.

For example, the invasion and settlement of non-native plant species have deteriorated the soil to the point of making the growth of agricultural crops impossible. The Katari River, previously used as a source of water for households and as a recreational and nature-connecting space, now poses a health risk to surrounding communities. The river also carries a large amount of floating solid waste that accumulates at the entrance to Lake Titicaca.

Furthermore, since the economy of indigenous communities is based on agriculture and dairy farming, there is significant community mobilization that has led to a work agenda that addresses and constitutes a manner of contestation to the current situation of socio-ecological inequality. The project presented by Newcastle and the Bolivia Node seeks to contribute to the implementation of this agenda proposed by the communities.

The project is part of the implementation of CT's WP3, which includes the documentation of contested territories and the exploration of the accumulation of territorial knowledge with indigenous roots as a common, since the biochar technology actually originates from the traditional knowledge of Amazonian indigenous peoples.

Description of the project

The process is structured through a **scaffold workshop**, with the singular aspect that represents being originated in *otros saberes*, and then becoming a part of formal scientific studies, to lastly go back to the community to become its common through the **technical workshops** and the implementation of the biochar filters in situ.

Timeframe

2023-2024, Katari Basin, Bolivia

Other representatives: The Machacamarca Baja and Alto Puchokollo communities, located in the Katari Basin on the banks of the Pallina and Seco rivers. Local Municipality government

Territory

The scientific work was twofold, with the Newcastle team learning, experimenting and adjusting the amazonian indigenous technology to the resources and requirements of the Katari Basin situation, and the IIADI team documenting the conflicts arising from the pollution of the Katari River and contributing to the participatory development of social innovative technology and interdisciplinary proposals for the local community solution to water pollution.

Likewise, the purposes of this initiative contemplated building a low-cost technology to improve the quality and volume of the water consumed by communities in both livestock and agriculture, as well as to serve as inspiration to local and national authorities in their search for sustainable alternatives to the precariousness of waste management in cities in Bolivia and the region.

Training and awareness workshops with the community

- Initially, meetings and field visits were held during the visit of the Newcastle team.
- Subsequently, virtual meetings were held for the pilot testing of the device in the Machacamarca community.
- The biochar device was built with funding from a B1 project and IIADI funding in the Machacamarca Baja community of the Katari Basin.
- There were a series of workshops for the community to debate, consolidate common strategies with the researchers and the local government, and improve the uses, preservation and appropriation of the biochar filters (along with the "biobarda", another technology implemented simultaneously)
- The biochar samples were then taken to Newcastle and analysed along with microalgae samples previously sent by IIADI.
- The results of the biochar analysis led to a second biochar filter implemented in 2024 in the Alto Puchukollo community in another area of the Katari Basin.

The technical workshops

During the initiative emerged the need to explain the community and local government the biochar technology: originated from the practices of use, care, and production of so-called "*suelos negros or terra preta de Indio*" (black earth) based on the ancestral knowledge of Amazonian indigenous communities, it had the dual function of providing nutrients to the soil for more prosperous crops and improving water quality.

In order to inform and understand the community perceptions regarding the implementation of these devices, a series of "training and awareness workshops on the management, use, and maintenance of the pilot solid waste retention devices and water decontamination system" were held in October 2023.

They were organised in 5 modules:

- Module 1. Introduction of all participants to create an environment of mutual recognition and trust.
- Module 2. Diagnosis of problems, needs, and positive aspects or strengths of the community.
- Module 3. Explanation of how the bio-fence and solid waste containment system work, and recommendations for its maintenance.
- Module 4. Use and recycling of plastic waste extracted from the bio-fence.
- Module 5. Water decontamination system in the Pallina River using biochar.

Through the workshops a physicochemical and microbiological characterization of the water was carried out in coordination with the communities as a basis for a dialogue of knowledge between biophysical scientific knowledge and local knowledge regarding the transformations and impacts on the environment and the lives of the communities surrounding the Katari River. The results obtained and the experience of the communities revealed the inequalities and changes produced by pollution from a historical perspective.

Additionally, it was an opportunity to share new technologies available for implementation and maintenance with various community representatives, using also a training guide designed to that end.

Biochar filters at the Katari River

Outputs and contributions to the contestation

The most evident outputs of this initiative are the two biochar filters (filters made from local biomass) with drinking troughs that have been built, allowing two communities to access improved water during the dry season, which is the most critical time in terms of both water availability and contaminant concentrations.

This technology -that benefits women the most, since they are responsible for caring for and watering livestock- helps restore water quality in the affected area and positions local initiatives as proposals for socio-environmental mitigation policies. All based on experience, the truly applicable otros saberes resulting from a dialogue between local knowledge and the prioritization of community needs, and the scientific knowledge systematized by scientific academia.

Furthermore, scientific knowledge has emerged, both relevant to the contestation needs of communities affected by territorial dispossession in the Basin, and to the scientific community of Newcastle on the effectiveness of the device and its applicability to different types of contamination.

Biochar filters at the Katari River

Community participatory, joint action was the key element in building solutions to the water crisis and the water pollution that affects them. The possibilities identified and the institutional alliances built during 2022 between cooperation agencies, academic actors, activist groups, and local authorities made these solutions a reality.

The contestation is, in this scenery, the response of the communities in order to recover the conditions of their territory and to propose low-cost public policy proposals based on scientific evidence.

This process has meant, on the one hand, a contribution to the immediate exercise of fundamental rights, such as the right to life, water, healthy food, and health, in communities affected by pollution, and, from a broader perspective, the right to a healthy, protected, and balanced environment; and on the second hand, through the impact of the results, has raised environmental awareness in the communities concerned and in the communities of the basin in general.

Further information:

Video

<https://www.facebook.com/IIADIOficial/video/s/cuenca-katari-sistema-de-filtraci%C3%B3n-de-agua-biochar/1135883848189886/>

Flyer

<https://www.facebook.com/photo.php?fbid=853203750328533&id=100069167462567&set=a.418390130476566>

Summary of the process

[Memoria-Soluciones-innovadoras-IIADI-2023 V final_compressed - Carlos Revilla.pdf](#)

Voces-Territorios: An app for mapping territorial processes

Lead network node

Universidad Autónoma de Madrid -UAM, Spain

Participating actors

Representatives of the nodes: Agro-UBA,CEUR-CONICET, ACIJ, UNSAM. Buenos Aires, Argentina

Other representatives: Universidad de Chile. GEMAS, Argentina. Pontificia Universidad Javeriana, Cali, Colombia. Researchers, artists and residents from the Programme “Tejidos Conjuntivos” (“Connective Tissues”) at the National Museum and Art Centre Reina Sofía-Madrid, Spain

Description of the process

This initiative sought to develop an app that enabled a collaborative approach for the co-production of counter-hegemonic maps of contested territories and territorial accumulation, being one of its main objectives to develop an Atlas of the processes of territorial dispute and accumulation in collaboration with local communities involved in the struggles in different urban, peri-urban and rural contexts in Latin America (Argentina, Bolivia, Chile, Colombia, Ecuador) and Europe (Germany, Spain, France, Italy, Portugal, United Kingdom).

“Voces-Territorios” is a citizen science initiative that seeks to enhance the visibility and reach for those communities struggling for their territories, especially in the face of processes such as extractivism, gentrification, and dispossession. It operates as a platform that allows people to share testimonies, photos, videos, and documents through a mobile app and website, mapping these experiences and creating solidarity networks.

The first steps started in 2022, with the decision to develop an application that would allow linking texts and emotional reactions to images and also systematize images and perform searches based on different aspects (territorial, purpose/function, authorship, languages, emotion/evaluation, etc.).

In the 2 following years the focus was to identify the needs for a plural system for collecting multimodal geolocated information, representing and analyzing information for the Atlas of Territorial Accumulation and to specify the functionalities of a multimodal citizen science application that responds to the identified needs.

These goals were achieved after the organization of two virtual workshops and one in-person workshop at the Mapoteca Amazonica meeting.

Likewise, two prototypes of the smartphone application were developed in those years, and the presentation of the third one was held during the MTM.

At this point, the second phase of the project started, with the objectives of launching, disseminating and collaborating with the adoption of the platform all through CT network, while simultaneously enhancing the app (and the access to it). Is within this phase that took place the two workshops documented below.

In Madrid

Date and location: March 20, 2024. National Museum and Art Centre Reina Sofía- Madrid, Spain

Description of the activity

Workshop: “Presentation of the Voces-Territorios citizen science platform and its pilot application for documenting territorial transformation processes around the Reina Sofía Museum”.

This technical workshop took place during the Seminar “Language, Power and Capital”, organised by the “Tejidos Conjuntivos” (“Connective Tissues”) Programme at the Museum, aiming on the one hand to introduce the researches to the platform, and on the other hand, to apply it in a

study case of urban transformations in the surroundings of the Museo Nacional y Centro de Arte Reina Sofía (Madrid).

In this study, the artists and researchers participating have mapped the Museum's surroundings, taking more than 200 photographs of the area with their descriptive cards, reflecting the urban, semiotic, and linguistic processes of that territory, which can be observed on the collective map. Touristification and gentrification replace local languages and names with generic English terms. Residents in the Juan Goytisolo and Lavapiés squares creatively defend their living spaces, while touristification transforms even warehouses into unaffordable housing and public squares into cafes. Mobilizations and stickers reflect the resistance and memories of recent neighborhood movements.

In Buenos Aires

Date and location: 22 October, 2024, Cátedra de Extensión y Sociología Rural, Facultad de Agronomía (Extension and Rural Sociology Course) UBA. Buenos Aires, Argentina

Description of the activity

Workshop: "How to use Voces-Territorios app (and what for) in the context of researching processes of territorial accumulation".

This **hybrid technical workshop** gathered researchers from different Argentina Nodes and consisted of the presentation and testing of the platform/app "Voces-Territorios" followed by a discussion of possible applications in different territorial accumulation processes.

The meeting intended not only to explain the uses of the app, or its technicalities, but to open the debate and reflection on possible applications in own projects and other territorial processes.

Additionally, it helped to get an insight into its ease of adaptation to specific projects and "*epistemologías otras*" by discussing the possibilities it brings to the communities to work with their own categories and perspectives expressed in the platform and Atlas.

While some of the participant researchers had already experimented with the app and used it to give visibility to their own research projects, some others had never tested it. The collaborative workshop allowed everyone to co-learn as well as to make contributions to the possible uses for the CT researchers themselves, as well as for the communities and researchers elsewhere.

Outputs and contributions to the contestation

The main outcome of this proposal is the development and operationalization of a tool for collaborative ethnographic fieldwork, in a citizen science strategy that integrates geolocation, semiotic, discursive and affective, visual, and other data, while highlighting the indigenous viewpoints and epistemologies of the subjects and agents involved in the antagonistic processes and struggles that are the subject of CT study.

This application is particularly useful in the process of constructing the Atlas of Territorial Accumulation and, in general, would be useful for ethnographic fieldwork at all CT nodes.

Furthermore, the platform allows for the collection and sharing of territorial transformations, and gives visibility to struggles against processes such as extractivism, gentrification, tourism, colonisation and land dispossession, and build networks between different communities and struggles, serving as a tool that allows users to collect and share their own vision of the territory: their own voices anchored in their own territories. Hence, the platform is a tool for resistance to hegemonic visions, narratives and projects (neoliberal use of territory), improving the potential of the communities for contestation.

Further information:

[Mapa colectivo](#)

[Taller: Cómo y para qué utilizar "Voces-Territorio" | Facultad de Agronomía - UBA](#)

Madrid technical workshop

Project Experimentation and Infrastructure Development

Urbanism workshop in Camino de borde - Costa del Lago y 8 de Mayo neighbourhoods of Buenos Aires, Argentina

Lead network node

National University of San Martín, UNSAM. Argentina

Participating actors

Students and Professors of: TEP-Taller de Experimentación Proyectual (Project Experimentation Workshop), LET-Laboratorio de Experimentación Tecnológica (Technological Experimentation Lab) and TU Taller de Urbanismo (Urbanism Workshop) at the School of Architecture, UNSAM. Argentina.

Representatives of the nodes: Basurama, Spain. Ciudades Reveladas

Territorial visit to 8 de Mayo neighbourhood, San Martín, Buenos Aires.

Context of the initiative

This research project is a collective learning experience for the development of community infrastructure in neighbourhoods without access to basic services, built upon a rubbish dump. The one year long **scaffold workshop** emphasizes listening to the inhabitants of the neighbourhood as a methodology for co-producing knowledge and participatory building of the commons.

Academic activity in vulnerable territories, through practices of listening and purposeful reading for the construction of facilities and habitat improvements, implies a new conception of the discipline and territorial knowledge. This type of approach has an aesthetic impact with a political dimension, which entails a deep commitment to the production of expectations that must not be disappointed, and which is directly immersed in the conditions and ways of life of people who entail a future fraught with various kinds of deprivation.

Timeframe

March 2024 to March 2025. Buenos Aires (Costa del Lago y 8 de Mayo). Argentina

Other representatives:

Centro de Investigación sobre Territorio, Transporte y Ambiente, Escuela de Hábitat y Sostenibilidad, UNSAM. DISU-Dirección de Integración Socio Urbana Municipality of San Martín. Merendero Rincón de Esperanza/Cooperativa 9 de Julio, Barrio 8 de Mayo. Cooperativa Proyectar Igualdad, barrio Costa del Lago

Territory

Argentina
Buenos Aires metropolitan area

Additionally, as previous experiences demonstrate that mobile technology fosters a more participatory approach to urban assessment, allowing for more dynamic and immediate involvement of residents compared to traditional participatory methods, it is hypothesized that co-assessment of public space in informal settlements, combining the results of technical studies with perspectives derived from participatory approaches enhanced by digital technologies, can lead to innovative urban diagnoses and proposals based on local knowledge and practices, improving habitat quality and the capacity to respond to various environmental challenges.

Furthermore, the information thus collected provides a more precise and immediate set of data, images, and locations, available for periodic review and evaluation, which is essential for implementing sustainable solutions over time.

Students' proposal for the project experimentation workshops

Purpose

While the main purpose was to develop an architectural and urban planning proposal together with the resident community of Costa del Lago and 8 de Mayo, achieving the production of a common good in an area of extreme vulnerability, the project also aimed to analyse the accessibility and daily mobility, waste management, and the creation of community networks.

Description of the activities

This **scaffold workshop** comprising an academic, curricular, and community series of workshops, as well as field visits and participatory meetings, was a year-long, temporary development which began in March 2024 and ended in mid-2025.

The undergraduate students and teachers of Architecture (UNSAM) explored the community's needs and struggles, and developed a preliminary project in collaboration with neighbours, representatives from social organizations, and the Directorate of Socio-Urban Integration of the Municipality of San Martín.

The methodology was based on the fulfillment of three concepts that are developed at different times: the **practice of listening, collective construction workshops and the "co-evaluation" of public space.**

- The processes of conversation, listening, and interpretation operate here as a design strategy and as a device for producing trust, reciprocity and affection. The development of these projects has an initial stage of conversation and public interviews, established as an exercise in knowledge collection that attempts to gain a first understanding of the topic and the problems to be solved, as well as to understand future projections and their limitations.

- The collective thinking exercise that then takes place consists of interpreting everything heard in conversations with the community and project users, and then developing a framework that brings together needs, physical and infrastructure requirements, the possibility of construction in stages, potential growth, hypotheses for flexibility and transformation of spaces, and an understanding of the project's ultimate scope.
- At the same time, the "co-evaluation" of public space allows for an understanding that goes beyond objective data from technical surveys, incorporating the perceptions and experiences of users.

The workshops and participatory meetings for the development of ideas and projects have been carried out during the year 2024, both in the Institute of Architecture and Urbanism of the EHyS UNSAM, as well as in the headquarters of the social organizations, the Merendero Rincón de Esperanza and the 8 de Mayo Community Center, and at the headquarters of the DISU (Socio-Urban Integration Directorate of the Municipality of San Martín).

There were three **technical workshops** held in 2024, which served as axes of the process:

- TEP-Taller de Experimentación Proyectual (Project Experimentation Workshop), which structured the groups of students in their collective work on the community facilities program, and where they formulated the different proposals;
- LET-Laboratorio de Experimentación Tecnológica (Technological Experimentation Lab) which organised the works made on the technological component of the project, always in dialogue with all the stakeholders involved; and
- TU Taller de Urbanismo (Urbanism Workshop) in which the proactive analysis of the public space was conducted, through meetings and visits to the neighbourhoods adjacent to Camino de Borde, including Costa del Lago and 8 de Mayo.

Territorial visits and Neighborhood mapping as part of the project experimentation workshops

The program has been developed collectively, and the students have formulated 12 different proposals for the site projects that were afterwards presented to the community with the goal of fostering a dialogue in which consensus was built and the advantages and disadvantages of each were evaluated, thus selecting the most viable alternative.¹⁴

Outputs and contributions to the contestation

To conclude the initiative, during 2025, the first phase of the community facilities is being built collectively, involving students and social organizations.

At the same time, progress is being made in the application of mobile technology to record the problems perceived by the residents of Costa del Lago and 8 de Mayo regarding the daily use of streets and corridors.

These instances of experience and collective work represented an opportunity to recover the social value of Architecture as a discipline, an opportunity to transfer the emerging social issues occurring in our territories into technical knowledge, based on the construction of networks with social actors, local governments, and the community.

In this context, these experiences are fundamental to the training of the students and have been integrated as a part of the program's curriculum. Although, it is important to remark that these projects are rooted in artisanal methods and are site-specific: they cannot be replicated uncritically, or subjected to rigid structures or procedures, as each approach deserves to be reconsidered from the very beginning. They cannot be considered as devices to be mass-produced, because each social connection, each material connection, each resource financing requires a specific method of implementation. Therefore, these courses represent a permanent challenge for the teachers and researchers not to automatise the implementation, which would make them lose their potential for contestation (both for the communities and the academy).

At the urban level, a proactive analysis of the popular neighbourhoods adjacent to the Camino de Borde was conducted in collaboration with the DISU (National Urban Development Union), focusing on environmental issues (waste disposal, flood zones, vegetation and absorbent soil), accessibility, the presence of infrastructure, and the configuration of micro-centralities. This work served as the basis for a subsequent, targeted survey of public spaces (streets, corridors, and sports fields) in the 8 de Mayo and Costa del Lago neighbourhoods, conducted by CITTA researchers and fellows.

The results of this analysis, consisting of a georeferenced mapping of variables related to the use and condition of these spaces will be presented in a workshop to be held in the neighbourhoods, where it is planned to work with territorial coordinators on the methodology for the participatory diagnosis phase that will begin in March/April 2025.

The development of a common roadmap allows for proactive readings on an urban scale and a series of architectural projects emerging from a core of agreed-upon needs that, in turn, interpret and find diverse work scenarios and are subject to different kinds of imaginations, which constitutes a manner of contestation in itself

Further information:

https://www.instagram.com/p/DIMQgPgxm3/?img_index=1

Territorial visit to Costa del Lago neighbourhood, San Martín, Buenos Aires

[14] In the end, the selected project was the one proposed by Valeria Martínez & Facundo Solfori.

Section 2: Performances and Theatre

Performances and Applied Theatre as Research Strategies

The body believes in what it plays at: it weeps if it mimes grief. It does not represent what it performs, it does not memorize the past, it enacts the past, bringing it back to life. What is 'learned by body' is not something that one has, like knowledge that can be brandished, but something that one is. This is particularly clear in non-literate societies, where inherited knowledge can only survive in the incorporated state. It is never detached from the body that bears it and can be reconstituted only by means of a kind of gymnastics designed to evoke it, a mimesis [...] (Bourdieu, Pierre: 1990, p.73)

A **territorial performance** is a “cultural device for exploring space and time through the body. It allows knowledge to be generated and transferred by bringing into play social knowledge, memory and a sense of identity through actions in the spaces involved” (Nanclares da Veiga, A; García Pérez, E; Ramos, J; Ugalde, N; Kanai, M: 2024, pp.34).

Unlike other forms of theatrical performances and conventional theatre, it has an “ephemeral character in a given time and space and can be a multidisciplinary discourse but always involves placing people's own bodies in the territory involved, seeking to question and mobilise collectively and politically around what is chosen to work on the chosen theme” (Nanclares da Veiga, A; García Pérez, E; Ramos, J; Ugalde, N; Kanai, M: 2024, pp.34). This people, involved as spectators and/or local participants, will not interpret a role as it is expected in a stage performance but will bring their own embodied identities into the “exploration of the bodily movements, gestures and sounds as an alternative way for the collective production of knowledge and generation of reflexivities” (Citró: 2016, pp.272- our translation).

The performative act itself may have a guideline - more like a flight plan than a script- but shall leave some room for improvisation. If pertinent, the deployed techniques may include the use of props and even building an (art) installation as a support for the evocative or sensorial exploration. However, most of the times, it is only about the bodies interacting within the site.

The territorial performance may be either the motive for, or the result of a research: its aim is to explore, to build and to disseminate new knowledges/ *otros saberes* and meanings, through alternative methodologies/ *otros haceres*. Thus, even if the spectators become protagonists -or “spect-actors”- in the process, it requires, as any research methodology, trained researchers, with a set of skills seldom taught in formal educational environments. In that sense, as we pointed out in the previous section, within the CT programme there have been several workshops aimed to train our researchers and to encourage them to incorporate those “*otros haceres*” into their methodological strategies.

That happened, for instance, with the workshop on creative exploration that José Vidal co-ordinated within the *Metodologías Otras* gathering in Chile where the participant researchers got to experiment with their bodies and emotions towards the construction of an investigative strategy.

Likewise, during the *Encuentros con el Agua* there were several creative exploration workshops offered, seeking to enhance the abilities and skills to endeavour to use this sort of methodologies, like the Dance workshop “*Cuerpo Líquido*” (Liquid Body), the one for “Observation and painting”, and the creative exploration workshop “*Itrofill Kúme Ko*” (The kindness of water in all its shapes).

These experimental methodologies -these *otros haceres*- do not always stick into a perfectly closed category: the ways of our quests interweave art and performance, either as an activity or as a strategy, co-living during the process and in the products of research. In words of David Atencio (2024): “The performance; this hybrid and spongy concept invites to move about different areas and, even, to get lost in between the borders that divide one discipline from another”.

In fact, although territorial performance originated as an artistic quest, it resulted afterwards in a transdisciplinary research strategy -paraphrasing Citró, something in between art, ritual and science (Citró, 2018).

This is the reason why we document and discuss in this section not only the performances that actually took place within the framework of Contested Territories, but also some other quests like *applied theatre* plays, or mixed products that, without being performances in the strict sense of the notion, draw on performative elements: we want to focus precisely on the methodological potential of performative and theatrical methods of research both for co-production of knowledge and contribution with territorial contestation.

As Peter Pekovsek explains, there is no consensus on the name of these unorthodox, heterogeneous forms of theatre, nor about their precise characteristics. For instance, **applied theatre** is a broad term for using theatrical techniques and principles in non-traditional settings and with specific goals beyond entertainment. It is also common to refer to it as **community theatre**, and moreover, in Latin America there are some specific branches, like **Teatro del Oprimido**.

“Community, applied or street theatre, in any case, is not a refined or professional product. Perhaps many of the participants have never performed before. The accent of these initiatives is on the process of construction, empowerment and contestation” argues Peter Petkovsek.

Nonetheless, there are some **distinctive elements** of applied theatre -as in contrast with territorial performances-. To begin with, the product (play) is the result of the research, rather than its starting point as it may be in performative approaches. As a second element, theatrical processes involve the co-creation of a more traditional script: even if it may leave some room for improvisation, most of the action is deliberately planned and rehearsed. And, most importantly, this leads to the notion that plays, through scripts and ulterior acting, work with words: in form of dialogues or monologues, as background effects, oral or written, the narrative relies mainly on the expression with words, rather than or articulated with expression with the bodies (which is the essence of territorial performances).

The third element of distinction we identify is related to techniques: even if non-traditional theatrical explorations make use of a myriad of mixed techniques, many of them derive from classic theatre antecedents, including acting, playbuilding, improvisation, storytelling, etc. However, some of the plays include other “less traditional” elements, such as art installations, audiovisual artifacts on stage, dance and even ritualistic moments, as it is the case of “Aillaquillén, the Island of the nine moons”.

However, beyond these differences, the borders between applied theatre and territorial performance methods are diffuse, and they share several elements: the starting point, for instance, is always based on the lived experiences of the participants. As Peter Petkovsek explains, “the first step is always to listen to what the community -or at least, those who are co-creating the play- decide strategically they want to address at that particular moment”.

Likewise, the participatory approach is essential for applied theatre and performative practices. The main goal is to engage the community in the process of co-creation in whichever role each participant chooses to play: from the exploration of memories and lived

experiences, to performing them, or simply as spectators who may discover themselves relating deeply with the narrative, beyond entertainment.

Additionally, both territorial performances and applied theatre plays usually take place in non-traditional/ site specific settings, instead of formal theatre institutions, which is not only consistent with the participatory approach and the aim to favour the community engagement, but also constitutes a strategy for territorial contestation and reclaiming.

Performance, Theatre and Contestation

In essence, both theatrical and performative research methods seek to explore the ways in which emotions, affections and senses incarnate in the subjects creating individual and collective meanings and producing everyday practices.

Thus, considering territorial performances and applied theatre as scientific devices puts into question, on the one hand, the very nature of knowledge creation and sharing, as it states that “what we learn by body” (Bourdieu, P: 1990, p.73) -either dancing, lying in silence or interacting with the elements- is not less important than what we learn through words. And on the other hand, it opens horizons for new territorial practices: while demonstrating that we can explore through senses those knowledges and memories sedimented and incarnated through habitus, and thus expose them, reveal them through “embodied reflexivity” (Citró, S: 2018 pp.3), we can begin to de-naturalise them, and even unbuild and unlearn them.

Reflecting on that potential, Javiera Cifuentes brings into discussion the power of these methods to dislocate binary thinking: “I think performance is, as David Atencio states, a lens through which one can look at the world, thus enabling us to see that there are other knowledges (otros saberes) related with the senses, with experience, with art and creation. And generally, they have been underestimated and undervalued by formal science [creating] a hierarchical binary relation between mind and body, reason and heart, masculine and feminine... There lies, I think, the potential of performance [as a means of research], since it’s something quite concrete that helps us see the world from another perspective”.

The deep comprehension of the nature of territorial conflicts and contestation, which is the one of the most important purposes of our network, requires the exploration through

creative and methodologies with the capacity to go beyond mainstream paths and techniques in order to sensitively connect with the everyday, incarnated experiences of the communities.

“Many times, they put into question whether this kind of work is actually art, or if it is a valid scientific method, or both” argues Peter Petkovsek, “and we may discuss largely what is art and what is science, indeed. But what I know for sure is that these simpler applied theatre plays have a direct, immediate and wider effect in the community”.

The theatrical and performative experiences of research we analyse in this section bring evidence exactly of that: their potential impact in the local communities and their ability to enable what Silvia Citró (2018) calls “practices of re-existence”.

“[these methods] try to actively convene the spectators to reflect and rehearse transformative and restorative micropolitics [...since] they are not hereby at the service of the legitimation of (...) social reproduction, but of critical reflexivity that enables us to imagine and also collectively incarnate -even if only through the limited space-time of the performance- another possible existence” (Citró, S: 2020 pp.11)

The Experiences

Strictly speaking, SILENCIO is the only performance that took place at this stage of the CT project. Nonetheless, as stated above, we include in this section the analysis of some other theatrical experiences.

Firstly, there were two particular workshops that worked as streams draining into SILENCIO performance:¹⁵ “AGUEAU VIVANT” and “CANTO AL AGUA” (“Song to the water”). Both took place during the same gathering (*Encuentros con el Agua*) and contributed to create the proper conditions for SILENCIO and eventually, for its replicas and new performances elsewhere.

Secondly, and besides the SILENCIO “family”, there were two additional experiences that we analyse in this section, since they play with performative elements as a strategy for research, if more framed within applied/ community theatre forms. They are “AILLAQUILLEN, LA ISLA DE LAS NUEVE LUNAS” (“The Island of the Nine Moons”), and “DÓNDE METER LA CABEZA” (“Where to stick your head in”).

[15] Somehow, many of the workshops and activities developed during the Encuentros converged in SILENCIO performance, more or less straightforward. For example, the workshop “Contemporary dance CUERPO LÍQUIDO” by Plataforma Azul, or “Observation and painting” workshop by Soledad Gattavara and “ITROFILL KÚME KO” (or “The kindness of water in all its shapes”) coordinated by Wüfko corporation, as many of the documentaries and shows that took place during the first few days, facilitated the exploration and connection proposed through the performance. For more information, visit “Encuentros con el Agua” in the previous section.

Performing on the shore of Mallolafken

Workshop-performance “AguEAU Vivant”

Lead network nodes

Universidad de la Frontera (Chile), University of Leeds (United Kingdom)

Context of the activity

This workshop-performance took place as a part of the *Encuentros con el Agua* gathering.

Description of the activity

“AGUEAU VIVANT” was directed by Peter Petkovsek as a workshop on performances, in connection with this particular body of water: the Villarrica lake/ Mallolafken.

Triggered by the question “How can we perform a lake?” or “How can we incorporate performance as a way of understanding and experiencing water?”, this small workshop convened around 15 researchers who were participating in the Encuentros. It sought to explore the relationship between ego and echo, individual stream and combined human-liquid element streams.

The aim was to learn and exercise performative techniques, dramatic composition, scenic creation and free writing, in order to create a still, embodied image of water, a tableau vivant (hence the playful name tableau/ agua/ l’eau vivant).

Performing on the shore of Mallolafken

Timeframe

November 15, 2022 -Playa Grande Lago Mallolafken/ Villarrica, Pucón, Chile

Territory

Chile
Pucón

Outputs and contributions to the contestation

This tableau vivant served as a closure of the workshop, and at the same time, in the words of Peter Petkovsek, “it was like walking in the same path as SILENCIO would (later), but in a smaller, simpler scale”.

It also served as a training for the participants to develop skills on performance as a means of research, thus contributing to future actions within the framework of Contested Territories.

Workshop-performance “Canto al Agua” (Song to the Water)

Lead network node

Universidad de la Frontera, Chile

Initial performative rituals

Context of the activity

This workshop was also a part of the *Encuentros con el Agua* and it was coordinated by singer, composer and aesthete Natalia Contesse. More than 40 people attended between researchers and the local community.

Description of the activity

It consisted in the sensitive exploration of water, delivering the participants with theoretical and practical tools for the creation and interpretation of a collective song to the element water. It was also an invitation to rethink the body(ies) of water as (contested) territory, enabling new imaginations of the site: a practise of re-existence around the lake.

The search was to activate the collective creative potential, using ritualised poetic word, together with melody and rhythm, to claim as a community the right to sing to the water. An artistic, aesthetic way to deepen our knowledge of water and create a familial bond with it.

On the one hand, the facilitator shared epistemological references of bonds generated between water and human beings, relationships which are both aesthetic and affectionate, always through a word transmuted as a sung poem.

On the other hand, they worked on learning vocal technique to enhance the voice and be able to sing collectively an ode to this liquid element.

Date and place

November, 16 2022 -Playa Grande Lago Mallolafken/ Villarrica, Pucón, Chile

Territory

Chile
Pucón

On the other hand, they worked on learning vocal technique to enhance the voice and be able to sing collectively an ode to this liquid element.

There was also an aim of growing the participants' sensibility towards water by recollecting and sharing stories and memories each of them had about the lake (or other body waters they lived nearby) and their presence in their lives.

Outputs and contributions to the contestation

These “tales of water” were, somehow, the raw material for the co-creation and composition of the collective song to the water.

The following day, this collective creation would serve as a silence breaker and closure to the performance SILENCIO, thus becoming a performative act in itself, and sharing its mid and long term effects and contributions to contestation.

More information

<https://www.instagram.com/p/Ckav8t1AePK/>

Collective song to the water

Performance “Silencio” (Silence)

Lead network node

Universidad de la Frontera, Chile

Date and place

November 18, 2022 - Playa Grande Lago
Mallolafken/ Villarrica, Pucón, Chile

Context

It was part of the programme of activities at *Encuentros con el Agua*¹⁶, an event that aimed to explore different perspectives to destabilize the traditional ways for comprehension of and bonding with nature, the elements and most particularly, water.

During the Encuentros, there was a myriad of debates and analysis that put into tension different notions of WATER as a resource, as a commodity, as a vital element, as site: as a contested territory. Along with other problems shared widely with other regions, the Mallolafken has a particular conflict with tourism and gentrification related pollution which was brought into attention during the gathering.

Description of the activity

This collective artistic action took place for the first time within that event: directed by Javiera Cifuentes Padilla, SILENCIO (Silence) convened more than 100 people among researchers, participants and spectators.

This artistic act sought to explore and connect with the essence of water by using the whole body rather than just mind or words, enabling alternative ways of knowledge co-creation. As Javiera Cifuentes states: “The main idea of this performance was to offer, within an academic context, a radically sensitive, experiential space: one that would invite us to bond with water in an extra-quotidian manner”

Elisa Avendaño Curaqueo and Natalia Contesse singing to break the silence

Territory

Chile
Pucón

Having this particular site a foundational conflict with its naming - it is called Mallolafken (lake of the white clay) in Mapudungún, the language of the native Mapuche, and Villarrica (rich village) by the Spanish colonizers- it seemed only adequate to appeal to silence in search of new understandings and senses.

With these ideas in mind, the performance created a chain of bodies lying down in silence for 12 minutes: human bodies of researchers and participants thus integrated to the body of water, become part of the shore, paradoxically embracing the lake while experiencing the impossibility of grabbing the liquid.

The closure of the performance was marked by a song: the “Canto al agua”, collectively created during the workshop co-ordinated by Natalia Contesse. She has been working for many years on singing workshops to co-produce songs as an offering for the Water, which in this case was meant specifically to be the closure of the performance.

Likewise, there was another song in Mapudungun by Elisa Avendaño Curaqueo: the singer, performer, *ülkantufe* and *ayekafe* (and the first Mapuche woman ever awarded with the National Prize of Musical Arts in 2022) brought into the scenery of the lake a very powerful sound to end the silence.

The visual documentation of the performance was done by researchers and collaborators, but there was a challenge regarding the feedback from the participants afterwards: on the one hand, there had been more than a hundred spectators, passersby and participants. On the other hand, as the director Cifuentes put it, the energy of silence had sunk so deeply in her (and their) bodies, that it was really difficult to think of a workshop to bring into words all the feelings, perceptions and ideas, immediately after the performance.

[16] see description in Section 1

More than a hundred people participated in the performance

So she came to the idea of a tool she called “stream of voices”: she asked the participants to leave their email addresses and then she sent a very simple survey to gather any comments they might want to share, thus fulfilling the research purpose of collecting new senses and understandings felt and co-produced during the activity.

Outputs and contributions to the contestation

This performance has had a strong and multilayered impact in the community. It had a lot of visibility since the previous days in media and social media, and during the act itself when more than a hundred people showed up to participate in different capacities.

It was an intercultural space for co-producing artistic, political and academic contributions, and served both as training and as a research path in the context of the Encuentros con el Agua. And it was taken as an inspiration for participants as well as many other researchers around the CT network.

As a matter of fact, SILENCIO was meant to be both site-specific and ephemeral: a one-time act to explore a singular, contested body of water. However, with the support of Contested Territories and the assistance of Javiera Cifuentes, the researchers incorporated this poetic quest and replicated it in at least 6 more locations, intertwining a myriad of diverse territories and its struggles in a singular call for protecting and respecting water.

As it happens when a stone is thrown in the water, the waves keep expanding the original movement, each replica becoming a new, singular movement in itself, and water being the omnipresent element common to all of them.

As the director says, “all this started with my drive to make the performance happen in every territory where it did, but it would not have been possible without the Contested Territories network activating its full strength to generate SILENCIO (Silence) in the conditions we needed. The work of each and all of the people involved was indispensable”.¹⁷

Javiera Cifuentes: “The question of **contestation** is terribly important to me. It has been a constant reflection, like an open question to myself. Because there are some moments when the horizon looks so dark, when we face systematic violence, extractivism, spoliation... Then I think: how do we confront this? What’s the point of art, of artistic practice? It’s an open question that brings a lot of noise and pain.

And as a form of contestation to all that, I find this performance to be a way of resisting, an alternative to the current ways of protesting. While contestation usually demands us to be active, to be claiming, reclaiming, denouncing, proclaiming, this action invite us to the opposite: to establish an absolutely intimate bond [with water], a silent, demure, simple, humble bond which enables other voices to surge; the voices of water, of nature... That is where I find the power for contestation of SILENCIO”.

More information

https://www.instagram.com/encuentrosconelagua/p/CkrDEOTJjfo/?api=1%2F&hl=zh-cn&img_index=1

https://www.contested-territories.net/atlas/pdf/AtlasAcumulacionTerritorial_Caso8.pdf

[17] Javiera Cifuentes says: “I’m going to name each of the people who collaborated, because their work is indispensable: I was a foreigner everywhere, so these people who served as hosts were fundamental to the community outreach, to technical logistics, to production, to management, to dissemination...”

Here are the acknowledgments:

As an inspiration and consultant for the original idea of the performance: María José Contreras

In Chile: Consuelo Sánchez, Débora Aburto y Hugo Zunino

In Bolivia: Windsor Torrico and Patricia Urquieta.

In Ecuador: Gustavo Durán and Manuel Bayón.

In England: Philipp Horn.

In Spain: Disbel Roque and Malú Cayetano

In Germany: Carolina Romero and Michael Janoschka,

Cameras: Daniel Cárcamo, Gonzalo Puebla, Hardy Cotal, Michael Lukas, Juan Carlos Mamani, Mónica Cataño, Walter Ilimán, Cristian Serrano, Philip Horn, Alberto Nanclares, Khalil Esteban, Dispel Roque, Noelia Ugalde, Rouven Rech y Julia Ramos

Edition: Hardy Cotal

Illustration of Mapa de Europa invertida: María Cicuta

“SILENCIO” around the world

While the main structure of SILENCIO was the same every time it was performed, it acquired diverse characteristics in each location. When she was consulted about these distinctions, Javiera Cifuentes made an important differentiation: the performances held in Latin American territories, with the participation of aboriginal communities, have included a ritual component, an ancestral element brought into memory and perception. However, in Europe the director explains she struggled to find this ancestral cosmivision among the participants, who were instead contesting and defending the territory from other living experiences.

They took the challenge to relocate the performance accordingly, finding in each case its potential for co-producing otros saberes and strengthening the common abilities for contestation.

More information

[Silencio por el mundo.mp4](#)

https://www.instagram.com/p/DCUXzq8xoV3/?img_index=8

Elisa Avendaño Curaqueo singing to mark the end of the silence

In Tena, Ecuador (Saporumi)

Lead network node

FLACSO University, Ecuador

Date and place

Tena, January 2023

Context of the activity

It took place during the *Mapoteca Amazónica* gathering in Tena, a city on the margins of the Amazonas River where the mismanagement of the mining, inadequate and excessive extraction from the river have been causing floods in urban areas, putting the lives of the population at risk.

Manuel Bayón took the initiative and together with Javiera Cifuentes they went door to door around the community discussing the idea of the performance, to be sure not to impose or to invade the sacred space of the river.

Indeed, one of the elder leaders in the community accepted the proposal and, moreover, made it their own: he co-coordinated the activity in which the other members of the community and the researchers who were attending the encounter participated.

Description of the activity

While Javiera Cifuentes says the structure of the performance was similar to the one in Pucón, she explains that the old man from the community asked for his name and other details of his participation to be known only by those directly involved in the activity.

This was, consequently, one of the peculiarities of this replica of SILENCIO: the typical discretion and intimacy of the performance were reinforced in this occasion, and the only way to be part of the experience was the embodied presence during the act.

Performance SILENCIO at Saporumi, Ecuador

In La Paz, Bolivia: Cantos y Diálogos con el Agua

Lead network node

CEPLAG/IIADI Bolivia

Date and place

Hampaturi waterfall, April 2023

Context of the activity

This new replica of SILENCIO was performed during the *Diálogos Sur-Sur* gathering in April 2023 contributing directly with one of the aims of this initiative (and the Task 4.5 of Contested Territories programme), which is to “Recover territories through art”. It was co-coordinated by Cifuentes and Marisol Díaz, Quechua artist and performer.

Performance SILENCIO at Hampaturi dam, Bolivia.

Description of the activity

The participants went to the Hampaturi dam and were walked by local specialists and activists through the current conflicts around this body of water: the community's struggle in the access to and preservation of water -and nature in general.

Before the acting itself, the local researchers made a contextualisation explaining how, in their cosmivision, the samiris (minor deities) incarnate the voice of the waters' goddess. The silence enables them to emerge and channel the voice to an artist of their choice.

The performance acquired, then, a ritual dimension: the 12 minutes of silence allowed a connection with the water which (or who) was calling the performers, and the song that broke the silence and gave a closure to the performance was the voice of the water itself, channelled by Marisol Díaz's voice.

More information

https://drive.google.com/file/d/1IFq6dV9KLPe4Rf1JUyZvy1-l_n3gMT9/view?usp=sharing

In Sheffield, UK

Lead network node

University of Sheffield, United Kingdom

Date and place

May 2023, Crookes Valley Park

Context and description of the activity

In Sheffield, the gathering was quite small and intimate, convening the academic community, as well as some organisations which deal with stagnant waters. Most of the impulse was co-ordinated by Philipp Horn, since as Javiera Cifuentes says, for her there was a huge language barrier (which was such a paradox, the main goal and instrument of this performance being to explore silence).

It also was the first European set up of the performance, where the director noticed those unforeseen differences between the ritualistic essence of the activities shared with native communities, in spaces considered even sacred many times, and this other experiences of struggle and contestation less ancestral and more rooted into activism.

Performance SILENCIO at Crookes Valley Park, Sheffield, UK

In Madrid, Spain: Calero es nombre de arroyo. Silencio por el Agua

(Calero is Name for a Stream- Silence for the Water)

Lead network node

Basurama

Date and place

July 7, 2023. Parque Calero, Madrid

Territory

Spain
Madrid

Context of the activity

In this opportunity, the joint work of Alberto Nanclares and Malú Cayetano from Basurama, and the director Javiera Cifuentes, enabled the construction of a network of organisations which have the preservation of Calero park as a common. In fact, through this park there used to run a stream with the same name, but around the 1960's, when the current neighbourhood started to consolidate and grow, the foundations blocked this body of water. Further works on the soil have, more recently, deepened the disconnection of the park with its hydrologic cycle and origins.

With that history in mind, the researchers decided to add a new title to the activity: "Calero is the name of a stream", and to start the action by walking around the neighbourhood and the Calero basin (which is still noticeable) reclaiming this space as a body of water.

Performance SILENCIO at Calero Park, Madrid, Spain.

Description of the activity

There was an extensive participation of the community, and the closure was marked with a song by the director Cifuentes.

After the performance, neighbours, artists and activists from the surroundings of the park engaged in dialogue, shared a snack and started very casual though deep conversations. The oldest neighbours depicted quite a nostalgic image of the stream and park: they brought to memory, for example, how they used to cross the stream in barges and boats.

The performance gave visibility to a literally invisible stream and to the circumstances why it has become unseen and almost forgotten. It also helped create new bonds with water in general and Calero stream in particular, while promoting and enabling the encounter of neighbours and activists to strengthen the protection of their commons.

More information

<https://elsoldelaconce.com/2023/07/02/calero-es-nombre-de-arroyo/>

<https://www.caminarelagua.com/paseo-de-agua>

In Karlsruhe Schloss, Germany

Lead network node

KIT, Germany

Date and place

July 13, 2024. Schloßpark lake

Territory

Germany
karlsruhe

Context of the activity

During the Mid Term Meeting of CONTESTED_TERRITORY it was organised a new replica of the performance. This time, it was destined exclusively to the 50 members of the network participating in the meeting.

The goals were twofold: on the one hand, to replicate the performance as it had been happening elsewhere, thus exploring the bond with water, the potency of silence in itself and as a means of contestation and the dissident essence of silence in a high-decibel world. On the other hand, it involved a training dimension for the researchers, where they got to systematise the previous learnings through the performance and its replicas (where some of the performers had already participated), and to improve their methodological skills for the incorporation of active theatre and performative techniques within their research frameworks.

Performance SILENCIO at Schloßpark lake, Karlsruhe, Germany

Three years later, in December 2024, when Javiera Cifuentes proposed to perform SILENCIO, it made sense for the citizens of Hidalgo that it was done in the margins of the river Tula. On this occasion, the actors involved on the field were the aboriginal *Concejo Municipal* (Municipality Council), the Gran Asamblea de Damnificados 2021 (Great Assembly of the Affected 2021) and a great number of neighbours and passersby. It started with a ritual, the Ceremony de Pedimento a los Cuatro Rumbos (the Claim to the four Courses/Directions), somehow returning to Latin American manners the director had perceived previously. Then they proceeded as usual with the 12 minutes of silence, and the closure was marked by singing.

The performance had an important impact among the participants, as well as in the general population through media.

In Tula, México

Date and place

December, 2024. Tula River

Context and description of the activity

The last replica (so far) was not programmed, strictly speaking, as a part of CONTESTED_TERRITORY activities; however it had exactly the same characteristics and development than those, and nurtured the same research. We take it as a proof of the unforeseen potency of this performance to keep growing and replicating in different sites, contributing every time with contestations

The river Tula area in Hidalgo had suffered a dramatic flood in September 2021, with devastating consequences: it provoked more than 20 deaths, loss of infrastructure, houses and propagation of severe infections.

Performance SILENCIO at Tula River, Hidalgo, México.

<https://oem.com.mx/elsoldehidalgo/local/pobladores-de-tula-participaron-en-performance-del-silencio-a-la-orilla-del-rio-18451405>

https://www.facebook.com/permalink.php?story_fbid=pfbid0xuFUJSJK5Yb1FibKQ1SnamwrqWn4ggW98LmRiENxbYvxiZ1aiADfcJJ7myMaXsq5l&id=100079757230047

Que ta coquille soit très dure pour te permettre d'être tendre: la tendresse est comme l'eau: invincible

André Bay "Aimez-vous les escargots?"

May your carapace be as hard as to let you be tender: tenderness is like water: invincible

Performance SILENCIO at Mallolafken

Aillaquillen -La Isla de las Nueve Lunas (The island of Nine Moons)

Lead network nodes

Universidad de la Frontera (Chile), University of Leeds (United Kingdom)

Scenes from Aillaquillen- The Island of Nine Moons

Context of the activity

Co-created by Peter Petkovsek and Alejandra Aillapan Huiriqueo during the stay of the former in Universidad de la Frontera, Pucón, and presented at the Lique Cultural Centre in the town of Villarrica, Chile, in 2022.

The lake Villarrica/ Mallolafken area is suffering an environmental conflict as a consequence of extractivism, gentrification and especially touristification: during high season the lake becomes “zone of saturation” when it is not possible for the system to process the pollution co-produced by human waste and fishery. At the same time, the surrounding wetlands and forests are shrinking due to urban expansion.

Additionally, there is a historical conflict among indigenous Mapuche population and the “*huinca*” (non Mapuche/ white people) which shows even in the toponymy of the lake (and others): originally called Mallolafken (lake of the white clay) in Mapudungún and Villarrica (rich village) by the Spanish colonizers, it is still referred to in both ways.

Description of the activity

The piece started as the result of Peter Petkovsek practice research project within the framework of CONTESTED_TERRITORY, joint with local Mapuche activist Alejandra Aillapan Huiriqueo.

Date and place

2022 Villarrica, Pucón, Chile

The initial aim was to explore the environmental conflicts and how they intertwine and are interpreted through the Mapuche cosmovision, and how (and even if) they could be “translated into intercultural theatrical practice and the performance of an environmental narrative” (Petkovsek, 2025, pp.189) which would also serve as a way of contestation.

Alejandra had found a very interesting and adequate narrative for them to work with: a Mapuche *epew* which had been severely modified in its spirit. An *epew*, in Mapuche culture, is a traditional tale, transmitted from one generation to another, generally in an oral manner. It usually involves animation, explanations about creation, reciprocity between nature and humans, etc. Most importantly, and beyond the entertainment it can bring, the *epew* is a cultural device with an educational purpose: to teach values, traditions and knowledges important for the community to keep.

This particular tale explains the creation of the only island in Mallolafken Lake and, oddly enough, it has two versions as the name of the lake itself. One of the versions, the most widespread, involved a Mapuche woman falling in love with a Spanish coloniser. It was, as Aillapan Huiriqueo put it, a sort of “Disney” or “Pocahontas” story (One could even find some Malinche elements in it). The other one, however, the one that Mapuche families (as Alejandra’s) had treasured, was the original *epew*:

[There was] “a young Mapuche couple who, in the excited expectation of the birth of their first child, disregard the practice of asking permission and showing respect and reciprocity in relation to the environment. While crossing the Mallolafken Lake, they are punished for this in the form of the strong wind *puelche* that hinders their progress. They realize their error and ask forgiveness of the elements who come to their aid, combining fire from the volcano [Ruka Pillañ], water from the lake, the wind blowing fiercely, and the earth underneath to create a small island on which the young couple can land and give birth safely. The Mapuche name for the island, Aillaquillen, translates to ‘Nine Moons’ in memory of this legendary event”. (Petkovsek, 2025 pp. 190)

That was the story they wanted to transform into a performance, a process of research that, through art, could contribute to reclaiming the narrative and territory. The process was, as Peter explains, very rich and complex, as they had the chance to take all the time it required for a proper intercultural device to be set. For the first two months, Alejandra generously guided Peter through Mapuche life, cosmovision and relationship with the environment. They gathered a group of 6 or 7 local actors, both Mapuche and Huinca, and started working and bonding together.

Once the troupe was set, they started rehearsals and by the end of Peter's stay, the play was ready. They presented it in at the Liquen Cultural Centre in the town of Villarrica.

Lorenzo Aillapan performing with traditional Mapuche instruments

Somehow, Petkovsek considers that, while co-creating the play with Aillapan Huiriqueo, he was performing, reenacting and embodying in his own life the same values the *Epew Aillaquillen* teaches: humbleness, reciprocity, respect and gratitude for the environment and local culture.

The result was, as this co-creator says, a very heterogeneous, unorthodox play which in 45-50 minutes, comprises several acts: A first one with a scientific approach to the natural history of the lake, more like a western narrative; a second act representing the scene of the young couple from the epew, that is, the Mapuche narrative; a third one which was mostly a dance act representing the four elements; and a fourth act mainly with music played with Mapuche traditional instruments.

More information

[Petkovsek, P. \(2025\). Aillaquillen: The Island of Nine Moons. Cosmovision and Animism in Performance. Fourth World Journal 24\(2\), 189-202](#)

Alejandra was acting and narrating in the play, and so was her father, Lorenzo Aillapan,¹⁸ who is a very important person within the Mapuche community. He is an artist and a wise man, an *ũñümche* (or bird-man) extensively known and admired, declared as a "living human treasure" in 2012 by the Chilean Ministry of Culture. In the performance, he played the role of a *kimche*, a wise-man -very alike himself- who told the *epew*, the real, original one, and explained its actual message to the community.

Immediately after the play finished, he made a solo performance introducing the Mapuche musical instruments and talking about Mapudungun language and culture in general.

Additionally, to mark the closure of the show, there was even an *afafan*, that is a powerful, collective cry that Mapuche people perform in important or ceremonial occasions. It invites every one of the participants to join and repeat the shouting, to reinforce the energy of the ritual (whichever it might be).

Therefore, as a whole, the final artistic product expressed a confluence of diverse methods and strategies: on the one hand, the more western performative tactics, and on the other hand, the traditional, ancestral Mapuche ones, including ritual components.

Outputs and contributions to the contestation

The process of co-creation and co-production of the piece made a multilayered contribution to contestation. The play convened, when it was showed, a large number of spectators from different cultural backgrounds and adscriptions, some of them becoming spect-actors in the act, joining the *afafan*, for instance; some others getting to know the silenced version of the *epew* for the first time; some of them, from the academic community of UFro, who had contributed with the research, assisting to a very atypical and powerful product of a scientific exploration.

Hence, this reclaimed narrative gained a vast visibility among very different sectors of the community, while proving it is possible to develop actual, effective, intercultural and alternative ways of both artistic and scientific co-creation.

[Aillaquillen: Cosmovision and Animism in Performance | Peter Petkovsek, MFA | FWJ Interviews](#)

[18] For more information about Don Lorenzo Aillapan Cayuleo https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Lorenzo_Aillap%C3%A1n

Ópera-salsa: Dónde Meter la Cabeza (Where to Stick your Head in)

Lead network nodes

Pontificia Universidad Javeriana de Cali, University of Leeds (United Kingdom)

Timeframe

Developed from November 2023 to January 2024. Premiere: 19/03/2024

Context of the event

This piece derives from the project Habitancia, and it was made possible by the confluence of the previous research works of Carlos Tobar and the Javeriana Pontifical University team, and the University of Leeds member Peter Petkovsek's stay in Aguablanca from November 2023 to January 2024. Together with the Son de mi gente association, they co-created this piece that collects and re-lives the memories of the birth of the neighbourhood and the building of the community of Aguablanca, their struggles for land and for peace, with the salsa music and dance as a common.

The premiere of Dónde meter la cabeza took place during the *Simposio Internacional: Convivencias y Luchas por el Espacio Habitado* (International Symposium: Co-existence and struggles for inhabited space), a travelling event led by the Javeriana Pontifical University node which aimed to learn from and discuss about commons, public deliberation and communitarian experiences of contestation in Colombia, with participants, both from the CT network (from Bolivia, Chile, Ecuador, UK -Sheffield, Leeds, Newcastle- and Madrid, Spain), and the local LGBTIQ+, Afro-descendants and indigenous organisations.

Description of the process

The process of research started with Tobar and his team networking and interviewing members of the community who manifested their interest in systematising their history as a community challenged by violence -as eastern Cali has been-, as well as for discussing and exploring in depth the effects of climate change in their environment.

Scenes from "Dónde Meter la Cabeza"

As a starting point, there was also an acknowledgement of salsa as a common: it was a shared language and a way to express, beyond its -not less important- recreational purpose. In the difficult context of violences of several kinds, it had contributed towards peace building. Actually, in the Marroquin-2 neighbourhood there was an ongoing project of a school of salsa for children... and an old dream: to create an Opera-Salsa to explore and share their lived experiences.

Carlos Tovar, about the "Opera-Salsa" idea.

I was initially inspired by an Opera Rock called "Ricky horror show", which is a very important opera within the LGBTTQ+ scene. And later on, during a Contested territories stay, I had the opportunity to know some other works of that kind, which led to talks with some colleagues about the viability of actually projecting ourselves in an Opera Salsa in Aguablanca district.

I think that perhaps that, the Opera Salsa, is a horizon that we haven't reached so far, but it is such a beautiful horizon! It enables us to think that it is precisely there, in that hybridation, in the space between scenic arts and music, is where we can imagine alternative methodologies to represent the injustices that our communities experience.

Hence I can imagine that it is there, in that long trajectory of joint efforts that communities from all around the world have made to present us with their own sufferings through music and dance, that we found the origin and inspiration for this process.

Scenes from "Dónde Meter la Cabeza"

As co-director and neighbour Angelly Álvarez says: "theatre becomes a safe space for the people who inhabit these places, and it can put into question things that happen in their communities, how they feel about all that, and all of a sudden, they can express themselves there, in that space, a non-judgmental space [...]. In everyday life in their territories there is so much that they need to keep silent about, because of violence, there is a mandate of silence. But, when they gain access to theatre, dance, plastic arts, well: there is a bridge for them to feel free, to say 'here I am, here I dwell and this is what I think about our reality, my life, my family'. It may become a space for talking" and breaking the silence.

As the researching team found out, the initiative was ambitious, since the "troupe" had dissimilar abilities to face the diverse demands: the oral and written language for the script, the acting skills for the theatrical parts, and the salsa dance for the musical pieces.

As Peter Petkovsek -script co-ordinator and dancers' and actors' co-director- explains, there are 3 important elements in a process like this: the first one is the **context**, which is never the same in one location or another. They had a lot of previous work done by the researchers and knew the territory, the community and their struggles. The second one is the **focus**: what of all that context, history, and identitarian elements is the community willing to narrate at this particular point. The third one is **building on top** of what is already well known, the group's strongest points, **their forte**, which in this case was salsa. They took the choreographies already developed and incorporated by the group as the raw material to express the critical narratives on the neighbourhood.

For 2 months they had a multilayered process of co-creation: they started working to enhance the narratological abilities of the participants to favour the resignification of the sources of conflict and violence, and thinking of viable alternatives, thus being also able to discuss the contents and the focus of the narrative, and to write the script. Simultaneously, they started adapting the choreographies to this new narrative, and, of course, rehearsing them at the same time as the dialogues.

Description of the activity

Finally, they built this unique, unclassifiable musical piece, *Dónde meter la cabeza*. Its title comes from a traditional saying "It's good to have a spot where to stick your head in", in reference to a place where to live, a home.

The first act narrates the arrival of a mother and her little daughter to the territory where nowadays lies Marroquin 2 neighbourhood in Aguablanca district. It's based upon Sandra's story, and shows 2 iconic moments in the history of East-Cali: the self-building of popular neighbourhoods in the ends of the XX century, and the conflict of violence the youth have been involved with due to lack of opportunities for inclusion, in addition to political and narco-violence contexts in the beginnings of this century.

The second act is based on the biography of John Murillo -one of the founders of Son de mi Gente- who was 18 years old when, on occasion of a robbery, was shot and seriously injured. He survived but has lived ever since then in a wheelchair. The musical describes how he had to decide between seeking vengeance or instead, as it happened, choosing to work for peace building and start the organisation Son de mi gente.

The third and last act explores the environmental impact of the creation of the neighbourhood, and the interactions of the different actors of the community within the land, which was originally a wetland. The environment becomes more than scenography or landscape: it is a living entity that evolves through the years, in the darkest times is used as a clandestine site for disposal of bodies, it serves as a foundation for the houses as families keep arriving and settling there, and finally becomes a green island, a space for restoration and conservation of nature in the centre of a very marginal suburb of Cali.

The premiere, as we said above, took place at the Javeriana Pontifical University and was offered for the Contested Territories members who were attending to the Simposio Internacional: Convivencias y Luchas por el Espacio Habitado (International Symposium: Co-existence and struggles for inhabited space). After the show, there was a dialogue and debate with the performers and the audience.

It was the only time the Opera-salsa has been represented in a "formal" institution: since then, it has been shown around 5 or 6 more times, always in open spaces like parks and streets.

Outputs and contributions to the contestation

From the co-creators' standpoint, the play is "a danced epistemology with a salsa tone". It reclaims popular knowledge and strategies proposed by the inhabitants of vulnerable territories to build peace.

Contestation, for them, refers to performative experiences that seek to demonstrate the impact of externalities caused by injustice. The historical processes show the insufficiency of the States to assist the citizens in crises caused by violence and rights deprivation. In this kind of theatrical methods of research we get to explore, identify and witness the definition of strategies based on grounded comprehension of the demands of cultural acknowledgement, economic redistribution, fair political representation and environmental justice.

Even if it was not part of the initial plan, the Opera-salsa premiere was kindly recorded and later edited and composed as a movie by Mónica Bravo Pedrosa, Manuel Alejandro Orozco Van and their students of the Javeriana school of Cinema. This unexpected product has expanded the reach of the performance, spreading not only within the CONTESTED_TERRITORY network and the Javeriana University community, but also all-around Cali and Colombia.

Last but probably the most important lesson learned regarding contestation was the contribution that salsa and performances can make -and have made already- as methodology and strategy towards peace-building. Taken as a starting point, a shared language and a common, they enable experiences of possible and desirable togetherness: the imagination and re-claim of territories of peace.

More information

Musical

[DÓNDE METER LA CABEZA](#)

Podcast with the team

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=lfmq7U8BCEc>

Scenes from "Dónde Meter la Cabeza"

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